

Universal Magic Squares of Type $4k$, $6k$ and $12k$ Using the Digits 1 and 8

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*The whole work is without use of any
programming language.*

Abstract

*This work brings magic squares of multiples of $4k$, $6k$ and $12k$ using the digits 1 and 8. Each magic square contains 12-digits in each cell. Just with two digits, one can have exactly 1024 different possibilities of 12-digits combinations from two digits. In case of $4k$, we have written magic squares of orders, 4, 8, ..., 60 and 64. In case $6k$, we have written magic square of orders 6, 12, ..., 54 and 60. In case of $12k$, we have written magic square of orders 6, 12, 24, 36, 48 and 60. All the blocks of magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 12 are with **equal sums** in each case. The same work for the digits 2 and 5 is done in Taneja [42], and for the digits 6 and 9 can be seen in Taneja [43]. The work on multiples of 3, 5, 7 etc. shall be done elsewhere. Later, the work shall be extended up to magic squares of order 128 having 14-digits in each cell just with two digits: {1,8}, {2,5} and {6,9}. In the first two cases the work is always **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, while in the third case the work is only **upside-down**. When the magic squares are **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, we call them as **universal magic squares**. The whole work is without use of any **programming language**. It is just based on the number's combinations.*

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1 Introduction

In the previous papers [38, 39, 40], the author worked with three groups of numbers together for the magic squares of orders 3 to 32. In each group there are only two digits, i.e., {1,8}, {2,5} and {6,9}. In the first and second cases, we have results as **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, while in the third case for the digits {6,9}, the results are only **upside-down**. In the

second group with the digits {2, 5}, the numbers 2 and 5 are written in digital form to have the conditions for **upside-down** and **mirror looking**. In the third case, 6 becomes 9 and 9 as 6, when we make 180° rotation. For the magic squares of orders 3 to 16 [38], **palindromic-type magic squares** are also given.

The whole work is based on combination of two digits. For example, 2-digits combinations of two letters a and b gives us 4 possibilities, i.e., aa, ab, ba, bb . In the similar way considering 3 by 3 combinations of two letters, there are 8 possibilities, i.e., $aaa, aab, aac, abb, acc, abc, bbb, ccc$. Complete details of these combinations are given in [38, 39, 40].

This work is for the magic squares multiples of 4, 6 and 12, i.e., of type $4k$, $6k$ and $12k$ using just two numbers 1 and 8. In case of multiple of 4, we have written magic squares of orders 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32, 36, 40, 44, 48, 52, 56, 60 and 64. In case of multiple of 6, we have written magic squares of orders 6, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36, 42, 48, 54 and 60. In case of multiple of 12, we have written magic square of orders 12, 24, 36, 48 and 60. These constructions are based on equal sum magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 12 in each case. Each one with 12-digits combinations of 1 and 8 in each cell. These magic squares are **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, i.e., **universal magic squares**. In case of magic squares of multiples of 4 and 12, all the magic squares are **pandiagonal**. We observe that multiples of 12 are already presents in multiples of 4 and 6. The difference here in multiples of 12 is that these are formed by **semi-magic squares** of order 3, with **different magic sums** resulting in a **pandiagonal magic squares** of order 12 with **equal magic sums**. Similar kind of work for the digits 1 and 8, and 6 and 9 is given in another papers [42, 43]. The work for the multiples of 3, 5, 7, etc., and the **bimagic** cases for the multiples of order 8, 9, 16, etc. shall be dealt later on.

The whole work is without use of any **programming language**. It is just with number's combinations. The study of magic squares of orders 65 to 128 shall be given in another works.

1.1 Blocks of 4

Making 6-digits combinations, of two numbers, for example, 1 and 8, there are total 64 possibilities. Let's divided these 64 numbers 16 groups of 4 each in such a way that the groups are of equal sums. See below:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
111111	181818	111118	111188	111811	111181	881818	118118	811181	118881	181881	811881	111818	881811	111881	881181
888888	818181	188888	118888	881888	818888	118181	188188	818881	811188	811818	188118	181888	118188	811888	818811
118811	188881	811111	881111	888188	888818	181811	881881	181118	881118	818118	111888	818111	181181	188111	118818
881188	811118	888881	888811	118111	181111	818188	811811	188818	188811	188181	888111	888181	818818	888118	181188
1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998	1999998

The above groups are considered in such a way that they are with their **upside-down** and **mirror looking** numbers. For example, let's consider the group {111818, 181888, 818111, 888181}. In this case, the **upside-down** and **mirror looking** numbers are same numbers, i.e., 111818, 181888, 818111 and 888181. The same happens with all the 16 groups. Making combinations of 16 groups with each other, it lead us to 256 possibilities with 16 members each. Based on these groups, we can construct 256 **pandiagonal magic squares** of order 4 with **equal sums** $S_{4 \times 4}^n := 1999999999998, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 256$. These magic squares are given in Appendix 5, and are numbered according to following Table:

Table 1.1.

1=(1,1)	17=(1,2)	33=(1,3)	49=(1,4)	65=(1,5)	81=(1,6)	97=(1,7)	113=(1,8)	129=(1,9)	145=(1,10)	161=(1,11)	177=(1,12)	193=(1,13)	209=(1,14)	225=(1,15)	241=(1,16)
2=(2,1)	18=(2,2)	34=(2,3)	50=(2,4)	66=(2,5)	82=(2,6)	98=(2,7)	114=(2,8)	130=(2,9)	146=(2,10)	162=(2,11)	178=(2,12)	194=(2,13)	210=(2,14)	226=(2,15)	242=(2,16)
3=(3,1)	19=(3,2)	35=(3,3)	51=(3,4)	67=(3,5)	83=(3,6)	99=(3,7)	115=(3,8)	131=(3,9)	147=(3,10)	163=(3,11)	179=(3,12)	195=(3,13)	211=(3,14)	227=(3,15)	243=(3,16)
4=(4,1)	20=(4,2)	36=(4,3)	52=(4,4)	68=(4,5)	84=(4,6)	100=(4,7)	116=(4,8)	132=(4,9)	148=(4,10)	164=(4,11)	180=(4,12)	196=(4,13)	212=(4,14)	228=(4,15)	244=(4,16)
5=(5,1)	21=(5,2)	37=(5,3)	53=(5,4)	69=(5,5)	85=(5,6)	101=(5,7)	117=(5,8)	133=(5,9)	149=(5,10)	165=(5,11)	181=(5,12)	197=(5,13)	213=(5,14)	229=(5,15)	245=(5,16)
6=(6,1)	22=(6,2)	38=(6,3)	54=(6,4)	70=(6,5)	86=(6,6)	102=(6,7)	118=(6,8)	134=(6,9)	150=(6,10)	166=(6,11)	182=(6,12)	198=(6,13)	214=(6,14)	230=(6,15)	246=(6,16)
7=(7,1)	23=(7,2)	39=(7,3)	55=(7,4)	71=(7,5)	87=(7,6)	103=(7,7)	119=(7,8)	135=(7,9)	151=(7,10)	167=(7,11)	183=(7,12)	199=(7,13)	215=(7,14)	231=(7,15)	247=(7,16)
8=(8,1)	24=(8,2)	40=(8,3)	56=(8,4)	72=(8,5)	88=(8,6)	104=(8,7)	120=(8,8)	136=(8,9)	152=(8,10)	168=(8,11)	184=(8,12)	200=(8,13)	216=(8,14)	232=(8,15)	248=(8,16)
9=(9,1)	25=(9,2)	41=(9,3)	57=(9,4)	73=(9,5)	89=(9,6)	105=(9,7)	121=(9,8)	137=(9,9)	153=(9,10)	169=(9,11)	185=(9,12)	201=(9,13)	217=(9,14)	233=(9,15)	249=(9,16)
10=(10,1)	26=(10,2)	42=(10,3)	58=(10,4)	74=(10,5)	90=(10,6)	106=(10,7)	122=(10,8)	138=(10,9)	154=(10,10)	170=(10,11)	186=(10,12)	202=(10,13)	218=(10,14)	234=(10,15)	250=(10,16)
11=(11,1)	27=(11,2)	43=(11,3)	59=(11,4)	75=(11,5)	91=(11,6)	107=(11,7)	123=(11,8)	139=(11,9)	155=(11,10)	171=(11,11)	187=(11,12)	203=(11,13)	219=(11,14)	235=(11,15)	251=(11,16)
12=(12,1)	28=(12,2)	44=(12,3)	60=(12,4)	76=(12,5)	92=(12,6)	108=(12,7)	124=(12,8)	140=(12,9)	156=(12,10)	172=(12,11)	188=(12,12)	204=(12,13)	220=(12,14)	236=(12,15)	252=(12,16)
13=(13,1)	29=(13,2)	45=(13,3)	61=(13,4)	77=(13,5)	93=(13,6)	109=(13,7)	125=(13,8)	141=(13,9)	157=(13,10)	173=(13,11)	189=(13,12)	205=(13,13)	221=(13,14)	237=(13,15)	253=(13,16)
14=(14,1)	30=(14,2)	46=(14,3)	62=(14,4)	78=(14,5)	94=(14,6)	110=(14,7)	126=(14,8)	142=(14,9)	158=(14,10)	174=(14,11)	190=(14,12)	206=(14,13)	222=(14,14)	238=(14,15)	254=(14,16)
15=(15,1)	31=(15,2)	47=(15,3)	63=(15,4)	89=(15,5)	95=(15,6)	111=(15,7)	127=(15,8)	143=(15,9)	159=(15,10)	175=(15,11)	191=(15,12)	207=(15,13)	223=(15,14)	239=(15,15)	255=(15,16)
16=(16,1)	32=(16,2)	48=(16,3)	64=(16,4)	80=(16,5)	96=(16,6)	112=(16,7)	128=(16,8)	144=(16,9)	160=(16,10)	176=(16,11)	192=(16,12)	208=(16,13)	224=(16,14)	240=(16,15)	256=(16,16)

1.2 Blocks of 6

As we have seen above, making 6-digits combinations, of two numbers, for example, 1 and 8, there are total 64 possibilities. Let's consider 60 numbers in 10 groups of 6 each in such a way that the groups are of **equal sums**. See below:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
111188	111811	881881	811181	111181	118881	181881	111881	111818	881181
118888	881888	811811	818881	818888	811188	811818	811888	181888	818811
881111	888188	118118	181118	888818	881118	818118	188111	818111	118818
888811	118111	188188	188818	181111	188811	188181	888118	888181	181188
111111	118811	188881	181818	181181	111888	811881	881811	881818	181811
888888	881188	811118	818181	818818	888111	188118	118188	118181	818188
2999997	2999997	2999997	2999997	2999997	2999997	2999997	2999997	2999997	2999997

The above groups are considered in such a way that they are with their **upside-down** and **mirror looking** numbers, except the last two groups. We see that in the last two group there are two numbers {118181, 881818} and {181811, 818188}. But these two groups are **upside-down** and **mirror looking** of each other resulting in same sums. Making possible combinations, these 10 groups, it lead us to 100 magic squares of order 6 with equal **magic sums** $S_{6 \times 6}^n := 2999999999997, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 100$. These magic squares are given in Appendix 6, and are numbered according to following Table:

Table 1.2.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1=(1,1)	11=(1,2)	21=(1,3)	31=(1,4)	41=(1,5)	51=(1,6)	61=(1,7)	71=(1,8)	81=(1,9)	91=(1,10)
2=(2,1)	12=(2,2)	22=(2,3)	32=(2,4)	42=(2,5)	52=(2,6)	62=(2,7)	72=(2,8)	82=(2,9)	92=(2,10)
3=(3,1)	13=(3,2)	23=(3,3)	33=(3,4)	43=(3,5)	53=(3,6)	63=(3,7)	73=(3,8)	83=(3,9)	93=(3,10)
4=(4,1)	14=(4,2)	24=(4,3)	34=(4,4)	44=(4,5)	54=(4,6)	64=(4,7)	74=(4,8)	84=(4,9)	94=(4,10)
5=(5,1)	15=(5,2)	25=(5,3)	34=(5,4)	45=(5,5)	55=(5,6)	65=(5,7)	75=(5,8)	85=(5,9)	95=(5,10)
6=(6,1)	16=(6,2)	26=(6,3)	36=(6,4)	46=(6,5)	56=(6,6)	66=(6,7)	76=(6,8)	86=(6,9)	96=(6,10)
7=(7,1)	17=(7,2)	27=(7,3)	37=(7,4)	47=(7,5)	57=(7,6)	67=(7,7)	77=(7,8)	87=(7,9)	97=(7,10)
8=(8,1)	18=(8,2)	28=(8,3)	38=(8,4)	48=(8,5)	58=(8,6)	68=(8,7)	78=(8,8)	88=(8,9)	98=(8,10)
9=(9,1)	19=(9,2)	29=(9,3)	39=(9,4)	49=(9,5)	59=(9,6)	69=(9,7)	79=(9,8)	89=(9,9)	99=(9,10)
10=(10,1)	20=(10,2)	30=(10,3)	40=(10,4)	50=(10,5)	60=(10,6)	70=(10,7)	80=(10,8)	90=(10,9)	100=(10,10)

1.3 Blocks of 12

As we have seen above, making 6-digits combinations, of two numbers, for example, 1 and 8, there are total 64 possibilities. Let's consider 60 numbers in 5 groups of 12 each in such a way that the groups are of **equal sums**. See below:

1	2	3	4	5
111111	111181	118118	111888	111818
118811	111188	118181	118881	111881
118818	111811	181118	181881	118188
181188	118111	181811	188118	181181
181818	118888	188188	188181	181888
188881	181111	188818	188811	188111
811118	818888	811181	811188	811888
818181	881111	811811	811818	818111
818811	881888	818188	811881	818818
881181	888188	818881	818118	881811
881188	888811	881818	881118	888118
888888	888818	881881	888111	888181
5999994	5999994	5999994	5999994	5999994

The above groups are considered in such a way that they are with their **upside-down** and **mirror looking** numbers. Making possible combinations, these 5 groups, it lead us to 25 magic squares of order 12 with equal **magic sums** $S_{12 \times 12}^n := 5999999999994$, $n = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and 5. These magic squares are given in Appendix 7, and are numbered according to following Table:

Table 1.3.

1	2	3	4	5
1=(1,1)	6=(1,2)	11=(1,3)	16=(1,4)	21=(1,5)
2=(2,1)	7=(2,2)	12=(2,3)	17=(2,4)	22=(2,5)
3=(3,1)	8=(3,2)	13=(3,3)	18=(3,4)	23=(3,5)
4=(4,1)	9=(4,2)	14=(4,3)	19=(4,4)	24=(4,5)
5=(5,1)	10=(5,2)	15=(5,3)	20=(5,4)	25=(5,5)

2 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 4

In Appendix 5 there are total 256 magic squares of order 4. All of them are **universal pandiagonal** with **magic sums** $S_{4 \times 4}^n := 1999999999998$, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 256$. Let's write the Table 1.1 in the following way:

Figure 2.1.

The following subsections lead us to **universal pandiagonal magic squares** multiples of 4, i.e., of orders, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32, 36, 40, 44, 48, 52, 56, 60 and 64. These are chosen according to colors appearing in the Figure 2.1. It is not the only way to write magic squares multiple of 4. The readers can chose alternative ways to write these magic squares.

2.1 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 8

Example 1. Let's consider 4 magic squares of order 4 of type 2×2 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$

In this case, we get following **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 8 with magic sum $S_{8 \times 8} := 399999999996$.

8x8	pan	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996
	118811881188	881188888888	111111111111	888888118811	188881881188	811188888888	181818111111	818181118811	399999999996
399999999996	11111118811	888888111111	118811888888	881188881188	181818118811	818181111111	188881888888	81118881188	399999999996
399999999996	888888888888	11111881188	881188118811	118811111111	818181888888	181818881188	8111818811	188881111111	399999999996
399999999996	881188111111	11881118811	888888881188	111118888888	811181111111	18888118811	818181881188	181818888888	399999999996
399999999996	118811811118	881188818181	11111181818	888888188881	188881811118	81118818181	181818181818	81818188881	399999999996
399999999996	11111188881	888888181818	118811818181	881188811118	181818188881	81818181818	188881818181	81118811118	399999999996
399999999996	88888818181	11111811118	881188188881	11881181818	818181818181	18181811118	81118188881	18888181818	399999999996
399999999996	881188181818	11881188881	88888811118	11111818181	81118181818	18888188881	81818181118	181818818181	399999999996
	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996	399999999996

2.2 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 12

Example 2. Let's consider 9 magic squares of order 4 of type 3×3 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$

In this case, we get following **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 12 with magic sum $S_{12 \times 12} := 5999999999994$.

12x12	pan	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994
	118811881188	881188888888	111111111111	888888118811	188881881188	811188888888	181811111111	81818118811	18888881188	81111888888	11118111111	8888118811	599999999994
599999999994	11111118811	88888111111	118811888888	881188881188	1818118811	81811111111	188881888888	81118881188	11118118811	88881111111	188888888888	81111881188	599999999994
599999999994	888888888888	11111881188	881188118811	118811111111	818181888888	181818881188	8111818811	18888111111	88881888888	11118881188	8111118811	18888111111	599999999994
599999999994	881188111111	11881118811	88888881188	11111888888	81118111111	18888118811	81818881188	18181888888	81111111111	18888118811	88881881188	11118888888	599999999994
599999999994	118811811118	881188818181	11111181818	88888188881	18888181118	81118818181	1818181818	8181188881	1888881118	81111818181	11118181818	88881188881	599999999994
599999999994	11111188881	88888181818	118811818181	88118881118	1818188881	81818181818	188881818181	8111881118	11118188881	8888181818	18888818181	8111181118	599999999994
599999999994	888888818181	11111811118	88118818881	11881181818	818181818181	18181881118	81118188881	18888181818	888881818181	1111881118	81111188881	18888181818	599999999994
599999999994	881188181818	11881188881	88888811118	11111818181	81118181818	18888188881	818181118	181818818181	81111181818	18888188881	88888181118	11118818181	599999999994
599999999994	118811811111	88118888881	11111111118	88888188888	18888181111	8111888881	1818111118	8181188888	18888811111	8111188881	1111811118	88881188888	599999999994
599999999994	11111188888	88888111118	11881188881	88118881111	18181888888	81818111118	18888188881	8111881111	11118188888	8888111118	18888888881	8111181111	599999999994
599999999994	88888888881	11111811111	88118818888	11881111118	81818188881	18181881111	81118188888	18888111118	88888188881	1111881111	81111188888	1888811118	599999999994
599999999994	88118811118	11881188888	88888811111	11111888881	8111811118	18888188888	8181811111	18181888881	8111111118	18888188888	88888181111	1111888881	599999999994
599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994

2.3 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 16

Example 3. Let's consider 16 magic squares of order 4 of type 4×4 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 16 with **magic sum** $S_{16 \times 16} := 799999999992$. It is given below in two parts.

16x16	pan	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992
	118811881188	881188888888	111111111111	888888118811	188881881188	811188888888	181811111111	81818118811
799999999992	11111118811	88888111111	118811888888	881188881188	1818118811	81811111111	188881888888	81118881188
799999999992	888888888888	11111881188	881188118811	118811111111	818181888888	181818881188	81118118811	18888111111
799999999992	881188111111	11881118811	88888881188	11111888888	81118111111	18888118811	818181881188	181818888888
799999999992	118811811118	881188818181	11111181818	88888188881	18888181118	81118818181	1818181818	81818188881
799999999992	11111188881	88888181818	118811818181	88118881118	1818188881	81818181818	188881818181	8111881118
799999999992	888888818181	11111811118	88118818881	11881181818	818181818181	18181881118	81118188881	18888181818
799999999992	881188181818	11881188881	88888811118	11111818181	81118181818	18888188881	81818181118	181818818181
799999999992	118811811111	88118888881	11111111118	88888188888	18888181111	8111888881	1818111118	81818188888
799999999992	11111188888	88888111118	11881188881	88118881111	18181888888	81818111118	18888188881	8111881111
799999999992	88888888881	11111811111	88118818888	11881111118	81818188881	18181881111	81118188888	18888111118
799999999992	88118811118	11881188888	88888811111	11111888881	81118111118	18888188888	81818181111	18181888881
799999999992	118811881111	88118888881	11111111188	88888188888	18888188111	8111888881	1818111188	81818118888
799999999992	11111188888	8888811188	11881188881	88118881111	18181818888	8181811188	18888188881	81118881111
799999999992	88888888881	11111881111	88118818888	11881111888	81818188881	18181888111	81118188888	18888111888
799999999992	88118811188	11881188888	88888811111	11111888881	8111811188	18888188888	81818181111	18181888881
799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992
18888881188	81111888888	11118111111	88888118811	11888881188	88111888888	11188111111	88881118811	799999999992	
11118118811	88888111111	18888888888	81111881188	11188118811	88881111111	11888888888	88111881188	799999999992	
88888188888	11118881188	81111118811	18888111111	88881888888	11188881188	88111118811	11888111111	799999999992	
81111111111	18888818811	888881881188	11118888888	88111111111	11888818811	88881881188	11188888888	799999999992	
18888811118	81111818181	11118181818	88888188881	11888811118	88111818181	11188181818	88881188881	799999999992	
11118188881	88888181818	188888818181	81111811118	11188188881	88881181818	118888818181	88111811118	799999999992	
888881818181	11118811118	81111188881	188888181818	88881818181	11188811118	88111188881	118888181818	799999999992	
81111181818	18888818881	88888181118	11118818181	88111181818	11888818881	88881811118	11188818181	799999999992	
18888881111	81111888881	11118111118	88888188888	11888881111	88111888881	11188111118	88881188888	799999999992	
11118188888	88888111118	18888888881	81111811111	11188188888	88881111118	11888888881	88111811111	799999999992	
88888188881	11118811111	81111188888	18888811118	88881888881	11188811111	88111188888	11888811118	799999999992	
81111111118	18888818888	88888181111	11118888881	88111111118	11888818888	88881811111	11188888881	799999999992	
18888881111	81111888811	11118111188	88888118888	11888888111	88111888811	11188111188	88881118888	799999999992	
11118118888	88888111188	18888888811	81111881111	11188118888	88881111188	11888888811	88111881111	799999999992	
888881888811	11118881111	81111118888	18888811188	88881888811	11188881111	88111118888	11888811188	799999999992	
81111111188	18888818888	88888188111	11118888811	88111111188	11888818888	88881881111	11188888811	799999999992	
799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	799999999992	
9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16		

2.4 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 20

Example 4. Let's consider 25 magic squares of order 4 of type 5×5 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 20 with magic sum $S_{20 \times 20} := 999999999990$. It is given below in two parts.

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 24 with magic sum $S_{24 \times 24} := 11999999999988$. It is given below in two parts.

24x24	pan	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988
	118811881188	881188888888	111111111111	888888118811	188881881188	811188888888	181818111111	818181188111	188888881188	811118888888	111181111111	888881188111
11999999999988	111111188111	888888111111	118811888888	881188881188	181818118811	818181111111	188881888888	811188811888	111181188111	888881111111	188888888888	811118811888
11999999999988	888888888888	111118811888	881188118811	118811111111	818181888888	181818881188	811181881111	188881111111	888881888888	111188811888	811111881111	188888111111
11999999999988	881188111111	118811188111	888888881188	111118888888	811181111111	188881188111	818181881188	181818888888	811111111111	188888188111	888881881188	111188888888
11999999999988	118811811118	881188818181	111111818188	888888188881	188881811118	811188818181	181818181818	818181888881	188888811118	811118181818	111181818188	888881888881
11999999999988	111111888881	888888181818	118811818181	881188811118	181818188881	818181818188	188881818181	811188811118	111181888881	888881818188	188888818181	811118111118
11999999999988	888888818181	111118111118	881188188881	118811818188	818181818181	181818811118	811181888881	188881818188	888881818181	111188811118	8111188881	188888181818
11999999999988	881188181818	118811888881	888888111118	111118181818	811181818188	188881888881	818181811118	181818818181	811118181818	188888188881	888881811118	111188181818
11999999999988	118811811111	881188888881	111111111118	888888188888	188881811111	811188888881	181818111118	818181888888	188888811111	811118888881	111181111118	888881888888
11999999999988	111111888888	888888111118	118811888881	881188811111	181818188888	818181111118	188881888881	811188811111	111181888888	888881111118	188888888881	811118111111
11999999999988	888888888888	111118111111	881188188888	118811111118	818181888881	181818811111	811181888888	188881111118	888881888881	111188811111	811118888888	188888111118
11999999999988	881188111118	118811888888	888888111111	111118888881	811181111118	188881888888	818181811111	181818888881	811111111118	188888188888	888881811111	111188888881
11999999999988	118811881111	881188888811	111111111188	888888118888	188881881111	811188888111	181818111188	818181188888	188888811111	811118888111	111181111888	888881188888
11999999999988	111111888888	888888111888	118811888811	881188881111	181818188888	818181111888	188881888811	811188811111	111181188888	888881111888	188888888811	811118811111
11999999999988	888888888811	111118811111	881188118888	118811111188	818181888811	181818888111	811181888888	188881111888	888881888811	111188811111	811111888888	188888111188
11999999999988	881188111888	118811188888	888888881111	111118888811	811181111888	188881188888	818181881111	181818888811	811111111888	188888188888	888881881111	111188888811
11999999999988	118811881888	881188888188	111111118111	888888118111	188881881888	811188881888	181818118111	818181181111	188888881888	811118881888	111181118111	888881181111
11999999999988	111111181111	888888118111	118811888188	881188881888	181818181111	818181118111	188881888188	811188818888	111181181111	888881118111	188888888188	811118818888
11999999999988	888888888188	111118818888	881188181111	118811118111	818181888188	181818888188	811181811111	188881118111	888881888188	111188818888	811111811111	188888118111
11999999999988	881188118111	118811181111	888888881888	111118881888	811181181111	188881181111	818181881888	181818888188	811111181111	188888181111	888881881888	111188881888
11999999999988	118811818888	881188888188	111111118111	888888181111	188881818888	811188881888	181818111811	818181811111	188888818888	811118888188	111181118111	888881811111
11999999999988	111111811111	888888111811	118811888188	881188818888	181818181111	818181111811	18888188881888	811188188888	111181811111	888881111811	18888888881888	811118188888
11999999999988	888888888818	111118188888	881188181111	118811111811	818181888818	181818818888	811181811111	188881111811	888881888818	111188188888	811111811111	188888111811
11999999999988	881188111811	118811811111	888888881888	11111888818888	811181111811	188881811111	818181818888	181818888818	811111111811	188888181111	888881818888	111188888188
	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988
11888881188	88111188888	11118811111	88881111881	11811188188	88188888888	11181111111	88818811881	18111188188	81888888888	11118111111	88881811881	1199999999988		
11118811881	88881111111	11888888888	88111188188	11181118811	88818811111	11811188888	88188888188	11118118811	88881811111	18111188888	81888888188	1199999999988		
88881888888	11118888188	88111118811	11888811111	88818888888	11181188188	88188818811	11811111111	88881888888	11118188188	81888818811	18111111111	1199999999988		
88111111111	11888818811	88881881888	11118888888	88188811111	11811118811	88818888188	11181188888	81888811111	18111118811	88881888188	11118188888	1199999999988		
11888881118	88111181818	11118818181	88881188881	11811181118	88188881818	11181118181	88818818881	18111181118	81888881818	11118181818	88881818881	1199999999988		
111188188881	88881181818	11888881818	88111811118	11181118881	88818818181	11811181818	88188881118	11118118881	88881818181	18111181818	81888881118	1199999999988		
88881181818	11118881118	88111118881	11888818181	88818881818	11181181118	88188818881	11811118181	88881881818	1111811118	81888818881	18111181818	1199999999988		
88111181818	11888818881	8888181118	11118881818	88188818181	11811118881	88818881118	11181181818	81888818181	1811118881	88881881118	11118181818	1199999999988		
11888881111	88111188888	11118811118	88881188888	11811181111	88188888881	11181111118	88818818888	18111181111	81888888881	11118111118	88881818888	1199999999988		
111188188888	88881111118	11888888881	88111811111	111811188888	88818811118	118111888881	88188881111	111181188888	88881811118	18111188881	81888881111	1199999999988		
88881888881	11118881111	88111118888	11888811118	88818888881	11181181111	88188818888	11811111118	88881888881	11118181111	81888818888	18111111118	1199999999988		
88111111118	11888818888	88881811111	11118888881	88188811118	11811118888	88818881111	11181188888	81888811118	18111118888	88881881111	11118188881	1199999999988		
11888888111	88111188881	11118811188	88881118888	11811881111	88188888881	11181111188	88818818888	18111881111	81888888811	11118111188	88881818888	1199999999988		
111188188888	88881111188	11888888881	88111881111	11181118888	88818811188	11811188881	88188888111	11118118888	88881811188	18111188881	81888888111	1199999999988		
88881888811	11118888111	88111118888	11888811188	88818888811	11181188111	88188818888	11811111188	88881888811	11118188111	81888818888	18111111188	1199999999988		
88111111188	11888818888	88881881111	11118888881	88188811188	11811118888	88818881111	11181188888	81888811188	18111118888	88881888111	11118188881	1199999999988		
118888881888	881111888188	111188111811	88881118111	11811881888	88188888188	11181111811	88818818111	18111881888	81888888188	11118111811	88881818111	1199999999988		
111188181811	88881111811	118888888188	88111881888	11181118111	88818811811	118111888188	881888881888	11118118111	888818111811	181111888188	818888881888	1199999999988		
88881888188	111188881888	88111118111	11888811811	88818888188	111811881888	88188818111	11811111811	88881888188	111181881888	81888818111	18111111811	1199999999988		
88111111811	11888818111	88881881888	111188888188	88188811811	11811118111	888188881888	111811888188	81888811811	18111118111	888818881888	111181888188	1199999999988		
118888881888	881111888818	11118811181	88881118111	118111818888	88188888818	11181111181	88818818111	181111818888	81888888818	11118111181	88881818111	1199999999988		
111188181111	88881111181	118888888818	881111818888	11181118111	88818811181	118111888818	88188888888	11118181111	88881811181	181111888818	81888888888	1199999999988		
88881888818	111188818888	88111118111	11888811181	88818888818	111811818888	88188818111	11811111181	88881888818	111181818888	81888818111	18111111181	1199999999988		
88111111181	11888818111	88881818888	11118888818	88188811181	11811118111	88818888888	111811888818	81888811181	18111181111	888818818888	111181888818	1199999999988		
1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24			

2.6 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 28

Example 6. Let's consider 49 magic squares of order 4 of type 7×7 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$	$97=(1,7)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$	$98=(2,7)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$	$99=(3,7)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$	$100=(4,7)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$	$101=(5,7)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$	$102=(6,7)$
$7=(7,1)$	$23=(7,2)$	$39=(7,3)$	$55=(7,4)$	$71=(7,5)$	$87=(7,6)$	$103=(7,7)$

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square of order 28** with magic sum $S_{28 \times 28} := 1399999999986$. It is given below in two parts.

28x28	pan	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986
	11881881188	88188888888	11111111111	88888818811	188881881188	81118888888	18181811111	81818118811	1888888188
1399999999986	11111118811	88888811111	11881888888	8818888188	18181818811	81818111111	188881888888	8111888188	1111818811
1399999999986	8888888888888	11111881188	8818818811	11881111111	818181888888	18181888188	81118118811	18888111111	888881888888
1399999999986	881188111111	11881118811	88888888188	11111888888	81118111111	18888118811	8181888188	18181888888	81111111111
1399999999986	118811811118	88188818181	11111181818	888888188881	188881811118	81118818181	181818181818	81818188881	188888811118
1399999999986	111111888881	888888181818	11881818181	88188811118	181818188881	818181818181	188881818181	81118811118	111181888881
1399999999986	888888818181	11111811118	88188188881	11881181818	818181818181	18181881118	81118188881	18888181818	888881818181
1399999999986	881188181818	11881188881	888888811118	11111818181	811181818181	18888188881	81818181118	181818818181	81111181818
1399999999986	118811811111	88188888881	11111111118	888888188888	188881811111	81118888881	18181811118	81818188888	188888811111
1399999999986	111111888888	888888111118	11881888881	88188811111	181818188888	81818111118	188881888881	81118811111	11118188888
1399999999986	8888888888881	11111811111	88188188888	11881111118	818181888881	181818811111	81118188888	18888111118	888881888881
1399999999986	881188111118	11881188888	888888811111	11111888881	81118111118	18888188888	81818181111	181818888881	81111111118
1399999999986	118811881111	88188888811	11111111188	88888818888	188881881111	81118888811	18181811188	81818118888	188888811111
1399999999986	111111188888	888888111188	11881888811	88188881111	181818188888	81818111188	188881888881	81118881111	11118188888
1399999999986	8888888888881	11111881111	88188188888	11881111118	818181888881	181818881111	81118188888	18888111118	888881888881
1399999999986	881188111118	11881188888	888888881111	11111888881	81118111118	18888188888	81818181111	181818888881	81111111118
1399999999986	118811881111	88188888811	11111111188	88888818888	188881881111	81118888811	18181811188	81818118888	188888811111
1399999999986	111111188888	888888111188	11881888811	88188881111	181818188888	81818111188	188881888881	81118881111	11118188888
1399999999986	8888888888881	11111881111	88188188888	11881111118	818181888881	181818881111	81118188888	18888111118	888881888881
1399999999986	881188111118	11881188888	888888881111	11111888881	81118111118	18888188888	81818181111	181818888881	81111111118
1399999999986	118811881888	88188888188	11111111811	88888818111	188881881888	81118888188	18181811811	81818118111	18888881888
1399999999986	111111181811	888888111811	11881888188	88188881888	181818181811	818181111811	188881888188	81118881888	11118181811
1399999999986	8888888888188	11111881888	88188181811	11881111811	818181888188	181818881888	81118181811	18888111811	888881888188
1399999999986	881188111811	118811181811	888888881888	11111888188	81118111811	188881181811	81818881888	181818888188	81111111811
1399999999986	118811818888	88188888818	11111111181	888888181111	188881818888	81118888818	18181811181	81818181111	188888818888
1399999999986	111111181111	888888111181	11881888818	88188818888	181818181111	81818111181	188881888818	81118818888	11118181111
1399999999986	8888888888818	11111818888	88188181111	11881111181	818181888818	181818818888	81118181111	18888111181	888881888818
1399999999986	881188111181	11881181111	888888818888	11111888818	81118111181	188881811111	818181818888	181818888818	81111111181
1399999999986	118811818188	88188881818	11111118181	888888181811	188881818188	81118881818	18181818181	81818181811	188888818188
1399999999986	111111181811	88888818181	11881881818	88188818188	181818181811	818181118181	188881881818	81118818188	11118181811
1399999999986	8888888881818	11111818188	88188181811	118811118181	818181881818	181818818188	81118181811	188881118181	888881881818
1399999999986	881188118181	118811181811	888888818188	11111881818	81118118181	188881181811	818181818188	181818881818	81111118181
	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986
81111888888	11118111111	88888118811	11888888188	88111888888	11188111111	88881118811	11811881188	88188888888	11811111111
88888111111	18888888888	81111881188	1118818811	88881111111	11888888888	88111881188	1181118811	88818811111	11811888888
1111888188	8111118811	18888811111	88881888888	1118888188	8811118811	11888811111	88818888888	1181188188	88188818811
18888818811	88888188188	11118888888	88111111111	11888818811	8888188188	11188888888	88188811111	1181118811	88818888188
81111818181	11118181818	88888188881	11888881118	88111818181	11188181818	88881188881	1181181118	88188881818	1181181818
88888181818	188888818181	8111181118	11188188881	88881181818	118888818181	8811181118	1181188881	88818818181	11811818181
1111881118	81111188881	188888181818	88881818181	1118881118	88111188881	118888181818	888188818181	1181181118	88188818881
18888818881	88888181118	11118818181	88111181818	11888818881	8888181118	11188818181	881888181818	11811188881	88818881118
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88888111118	188888888881	81111811111	11188188888	88881111118	118888888881	88111811111	1181188888	88818811118	11811888881
11118811111	81111188888	18888811118	88881888881	11188811111	88111188888	11888811118	88818888881	11811811111	88188818888
18888818888	88888181111	11118888881	88111111118	11888818888	88881811111	11188888881	88188811118	11811188888	88818881111
81111888811	1111811188	88888118888	11888888111	88111888811	1118811188	88881118888	11811881111	88188888811	1181111188
88888111188	188888888811	81111881111	1118818888	88881111188	118888888811	88111881111	1181118888	88818811188	11811888811
11118881111	8111118888	18888811188	88881888811	11188881111	8811118888	11888811188	88818888811	11811881111	88188818888
18888818888	88888188111	11118888811	88111111188	11888818888	88881881111	11188888811	88188811188	1181118888	88818881111
81111888188	1111811811	88888118111	118888881888	88111888188	1118811811	88881118111	11811881888	88188888188	1181111811
88888111811	188888888188	81111881888	1118818111	88881111811	118888888188	88111881888	1181118111	88818811811	11811888188
11118881888	8111118111	18888811811	88881888188	11188881888	8811118111	11888811811	88818888188	11811881888	88188818111
18888818111	888881881888	11118888188	88111111811	11888818111	88881881888	11188888188	88188811811	1181118111	888188881888
81111888818	1111811181	88888181111	118888818888	88111888818	1118811181	88881181111	11811818888	88188888818	1181111181
88888111181	188888888818	81111818888	11188181111	88881111181	118888888818	88111818888	11811811111	88818811181	11811888818
11118818888	81111181111	18888811181	88881888818	11188818888	88111181111	11888811181	88818888818	11811818888	88188818111
18888818111	888881818888	11118888818	88111111181	11888818111	88881818888	11188888818	88188811181	11811181111	888188818888
811118881818	11118118181	88888181811	118888818188	881118881818	11188118181	88881181811	11811818188	881888881818	1181118181
88888118181	1888888881818	81111818188	11188181811	88881118181	1188888881818	88111818188	11811818111	88818818181	11811881818
11118818188	81111181811	18888818181	888818881818	11188818188	88111181811	11888818181	888188881818	11811818188	881888181811
188888181811	888881818188	11118881818	88111118181	118888181811	88881818188	111888881818	881888118181	11811181811	888188818188
1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19

1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986
888188118811	18111881188	818888888888	11118111111	888818118811	181811881188	818188888888	11818111111	881818118811	1399999999986	1399999999986
881888881188	111181118811	888818111111	181118888888	818888881188	118181118811	881818111111	181811888888	818188881188	1399999999986	1399999999986
118111111111	888818888888	111181881188	818888118811	181111111111	881818888888	118181881188	818188118811	181811111111	1399999999986	1399999999986
111811888888	818888111111	181111188111	888818881188	111181888888	818188111111	181811188111	881818881188	118181888888	1399999999986	1399999999986
888188188881	18111811118	818888818181	111181181818	888818188881	18181811118	818188818181	118181181818	881818188881	1399999999986	1399999999986
881888811118	111181188881	888818181818	181118181818	818888811118	118181188881	881818181818	181811818181	818188811118	1399999999986	1399999999986
118111818181	888818818181	111181811118	818888188881	181111818181	881818818181	1181811118	818188188881	181811181818	1399999999986	1399999999986
111811818181	818888181818	18111188881	888818811118	111181818181	818188181818	18181188881	881818811118	118181818181	1399999999986	1399999999986
888188188888	18111811111	818888888881	11118111118	888818188888	18181811111	818188888881	11818111118	881818188888	1399999999986	1399999999986
881888811111	111181188888	888818111118	18111888881	818888811111	118181188888	881818111118	181811888881	818188811111	1399999999986	1399999999986
118111111118	888818888881	111181811111	818888188888	181111111118	881818888881	118181811111	818188188888	181811111118	1399999999986	1399999999986
111811888881	81888811118	18111188888	888818811111	111181888881	81818811118	18181188888	881818811111	118181888881	1399999999986	1399999999986
888188118888	18111881111	818888888811	11118111188	888818118888	18181881111	818188888811	11818111188	881818118888	1399999999986	1399999999986
881888881111	111181118888	888818111188	18111888811	818888881111	118181118888	881818111188	181811888811	818188881111	1399999999986	1399999999986
118111111188	888818888811	111181881111	818888118888	181111111188	881818888811	118181881111	818188118888	181811111188	1399999999986	1399999999986
111811888811	81888811188	18111188888	888818881111	111181888811	81818811188	18181188888	881818881111	118181888811	1399999999986	1399999999986
888188118111	18111881888	818888888188	11118111811	888818118111	181811881888	818188888188	11818111811	881818118111	1399999999986	1399999999986
881888881888	111181118111	888818111811	18111888188	818888881888	118181118111	881818111811	181811888188	818188881888	1399999999986	1399999999986
118111118111	888818888188	111181881888	818888118111	181111118111	881818888188	118181881888	818188118111	181811118111	1399999999986	1399999999986
111811888188	81888811811	18111118111	888818881888	111181888188	81818811811	18181118111	881818881888	118181888188	1399999999986	1399999999986
888188181111	18111818888	818888888818	11118111181	888818181111	181811818888	818188888818	11818111181	881818181111	1399999999986	1399999999986
881888818888	111181181111	888818111181	18111888818	818888818888	118181181111	881818111181	181811888818	818188818888	1399999999986	1399999999986
11811111181	888818888818	111181818888	818888181111	18111111181	881818888818	118181818888	818188181111	18181111181	1399999999986	1399999999986
111811888818	81888811181	18111181111	888818818888	111181888818	81818811181	181811181111	881818818888	118181888818	1399999999986	1399999999986
888188181811	18111818188	818888881818	111181118181	888818181811	181811818188	818188881818	118181118181	881818181811	1399999999986	1399999999986
881888818188	111181181811	888818118181	18111881818	818888818188	118181181811	881818118181	181811881818	818188818188	1399999999986	1399999999986
11811118181	888818881818	111181818188	818888181811	18111118181	881818881818	118181818188	818188181811	18181118181	1399999999986	1399999999986
111811881818	818888118181	18111181811	888818818188	111181881818	818188118181	181811181811	881818818188	118181881818	1399999999986	1399999999986
1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986	1399999999986
20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28		

2.7 Universal Pandigital Magic Squares of Order 32

Example 7. Let's consider 64 magic squares of order 4 of type 8×8 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$	$97=(1,7)$	$113=(1,8)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$	$98=(2,7)$	$114=(2,8)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$	$99=(3,7)$	$115=(3,8)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$	$100=(4,7)$	$116=(4,8)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$	$101=(5,7)$	$117=(5,8)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$	$102=(6,7)$	$118=(6,8)$
$7=(7,1)$	$23=(7,2)$	$39=(7,3)$	$55=(7,4)$	$71=(7,5)$	$87=(7,6)$	$103=(7,7)$	$119=(7,8)$
$8=(8,1)$	$24=(8,2)$	$40=(8,3)$	$56=(8,4)$	$72=(8,5)$	$88=(8,6)$	$104=(8,7)$	$120=(8,8)$

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 32 with magic sum $S_{32 \times 32} := 159999999999984$. It is given below in two parts.

32x32	pan	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984
	118811881188	881188888888	111111111111	888888118811	188881881188	811188888888	181818111111	818181188111	188888881188	811118888888
1599999999984	111111188111	888888111111	118811888888	881188881188	181818188111	818181111111	188881888888	81118881188	11118188111	888881111111
1599999999984	888888888888	11111881188	881188118811	118811111111	818181888888	181818881188	81118188111	188881111111	888881888888	11118881188
1599999999984	881188111111	118811188111	888888881188	111118888888	811181111111	188881188111	818181881188	181818888888	811111111111	188888118811
1599999999984	118811811118	881188818181	11111181818	888888188881	188881811118	81118818181	181818181818	81818188881	188888811118	81111818181
1599999999984	11111188881	888888181818	118811818181	881188811118	181818188881	818181818181	188881818181	81118811118	11118188881	88888181818
1599999999984	888888818181	11111811118	881188188881	11881181818	818181818181	181818811118	81118188881	18888181818	888881818181	11118811118
1599999999984	881188181818	11881188881	888888811118	11111818181	81118181818	18888188881	818181811118	181818818181	81111181818	188888188881
1599999999984	118811811111	88118888881	11111111118	888888188881	188881811111	81118888881	181818111118	81818188888	188888811111	81111888881
1599999999984	11111188888	888888111118	118811888881	881188811111	181818188888	818181111118	188881888881	811188111111	11118188888	888881111118
1599999999984	888888888881	111118111111	881188188888	118811111118	818181888881	181818811111	81118188888	188881111118	888881888881	111188111111
1599999999984	881188111118	11881188888	888888811111	11111888881	811181111118	18888188888	818181811111	181818888881	811111111118	188888188888
1599999999984	118811881111	881188888811	111111111188	888888118888	188881881111	81118888811	181818111188	81818118888	188888881111	81111888811
1599999999984	11111188888	888888111188	118811888811	881188881111	181818188888	818181111188	188881888811	811188811111	11118188888	888881111188
1599999999984	8888888888811	111118811111	881188188888	118811111188	818181888881	181818881111	81118188888	188881111188	888881888811	111188811111
1599999999984	881188111188	118811188888	888888881111	11111888881	811181111188	18888188888	818181881111	181818888881	811111111188	188888188888
1599999999984	118811881888	881188888188	111111118111	888888181111	188881881888	81118888188	181818118111	818181181111	188888881888	81111888188
1599999999984	111111818111	888888118111	118811888188	881188881888	181818181111	818181118111	188881888188	81118881888	111181818111	888881118111
1599999999984	888888888188	11111881888	881188181111	118811118111	818181888188	181818881888	811181811111	188881118111	888881888188	11118881888
1599999999984	881188118111	118811181111	888888881888	11111888188	811181118111	188881181111	818181881888	181818888188	811111118111	188888181111
1599999999984	118811818888	88118888818	1111111181	888888181111	188881818888	8111888818	1818181181	818181811111	18888888888	81111888818
1599999999984	111111811111	888888111181	118811888818	881188818888	181818181111	81818111181	188881888818	81118818888	111181811111	88888111181
1599999999984	888888888818	11111818888	881188181111	1188111181	818181888818	181818881888	811181811111	18888111181	888881888818	11118818888
1599999999984	881188118111	118811811111	888888881888	11111888818	8111811181	188881811111	818181818888	181818888818	8111111181	188888181111
1599999999984	118811818188	881188881818	1111118181	888888181811	188881818188	81118881818	18181818181	818181818111	188888818188	81111881818
1599999999984	111111818111	88888818181	118811881818	881188818188	181818181811	818181118181	188881881818	81118818188	111181818111	88888118181
1599999999984	888888881818	11111818188	881188181811	118811118181	818181881818	181818881888	811181818111	188881118181	888881881818	11118818188
1599999999984	881188118181	118811818111	888888881888	11111888818	811181118181	188881818111	818181818888	181818888818	811111118181	188888181811
1599999999984	118811818181	881188881881	11111181818	888888188188	188881818181	81118881881	181818181818	81818188188	188888818181	81111881881
1599999999984	11111188188	888888181818	118811881881	881188818111	181818188188	818181118181	188881881881	811188181811	11118188188	888881181818
1599999999984	888888881881	111118181811	881188188188	1188111181818	818181881881	181818881811	81118188188	1888811181818	888881881881	111188181811
1599999999984	881188118118	11881188188	888888818111	11111881881	811181118118	18888188188	818181818111	181818881881	811111118118	188888188188
	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984
1111811111	8888118811	1188888188	8811188888	1118811111	8881118811	1181188188	8818888888	1181111111	8881881881	1811188188	8188888888
1888888888	8111188188	1118818811	8888111111	1188888888	8811188188	1181118811	8881881111	1181188888	8818888188	1118118811	8888181111
8111118811	1888811111	8888188888	1118888188	8811118811	1188811111	8881888888	118188188	8818881881	1181111111	8888188888	1118188188
8888188188	1111888888	8811111111	1188881881	8888188188	1118888888	8818881111	1181118811	8881888188	1181188888	8188881111	1811118811
1111818181	8888188881	1188881118	8811181818	1118818181	8888118881	1181181118	8818881818	1181181818	8881881881	1811181118	8188881818
1888881818	8111181118	1118818881	8888118181	1188881818	8811181118	1181188881	8881881818	1181181818	8818881118	1118118881	8888181818
8111188881	1888818181	8888181818	1118881118	8811118881	1188818181	8881888181	1181811118	8818881881	1181118181	8888188181	1118181118
8888181118	1111881818	8811118181	1188818881	8888181118	1118881818	8818881818	1181118881	8881881118	1181181818	8188881818	1811118881
1111811118	8888188888	1188881111	8811188881	1118811118	8888118888	1181181111	8818888881	1181111118	8881881888	1811181111	8188888881
1888888881	8111181111	1118818888	8888111118	1188888881	8811181111	1181188888	8881881118	1181188881	8818881111	1118118888	8888181118
8111188888	1888811118	8888188881	1118881111	8811118888	1188811118	8881888881	1181811111	8818881888	1181111118	8888188881	1118181111
8888181111	1111888881	8811111118	1188818888	8888181111	1118888881	8818881118	1181118888	8881881111	1181188881	8188881118	1811118888
1111811188	8888118888	1188881111	8811188881	1118811188	8888118888	1181188111	8818888881	1181111188	8881881888	1811188111	8188888881
1888888881	8111188111	1118818888	8888111188	1188888881	8811188111	1181118888	8881881188	1181188881	8818888111	1118118888	8888181188
8111118888	1888811188	8888188811	1118881111	8811118888	1188811188	8881888881	1181881111	8818881888	1181111188	8888188881	1118188111
8888188111	1111888881	8811111188	1188818888	8888188111	1118888881	8818881188	1181118888	8881881111	1181188881	8188881188	1811118888
1111811811	8888118111	1188881888	8811188818	1118811811	8888118111	1181188188	8818888818	1181111811	8881881811	1811188188	8188888818
1888888818	8111188188	1118818111	8888111811	1188888818	8811188188	1181118111	8881881181	1181188188	8818888188	1118118111	8888181181
8111118111	1888811811	8888188818	1118881888	8811118111	1188811811	8881888818	1181881888	8818881811	1181111811	8888188818	1118188188
8888188188	1111888818	8811111811	1188881811	8888188188	1118888818	8818881181	1181118111	8881888188	1181188818	8188881181	1811118111
1111811818	8888181111	1188881888	8811188818	1118811818	8888118111	1181181888	8818888818	1181111818	8881881811	1811181888	8188888818
1888888818	8111181888	1118818111	8888111818	1188888818	8811181888	1181181111	8881881181	1181188818	8818888188	1118181111	8888181181
8111181811	1888811818	8888188818	1118881888	8811118181	1188811818	8881888818	1181818888	8818881811	1181111818	8888188818	1118181888
8888181888	1111888818	8811111818	1188881811	8888181888	1118888818	8818881181	1181118111	8881888188	1181188818	8188881181	1811118111
1111818181	8888181811	1188881888	8811188818	1118818181	8888118181	1181181888	8818888818	1181111818	8881881811	1811181888	8188888818
1888888818	8111181888	1118818111	8888111818	1188888818	8811181888	1181181111	8881881181	1181188818	8818888188	1118181111	8888181181
8111181811	1888811818	8888188818	1118881888	8811118181	1188811818	8881888818	1181818888	8818881811	1181111818	8888188818	1118181888
8888181888	1111888818	8811111818	1188881811	8888181888	1118888818	8818881181	1181118111	8881888188	1181188818	8188881181	1811118111
1111818181	8888188188	1188881811	8811188188	1118818181	8888118818	1181181811	8818888818	1181111818	8881881881	1811181811	8188888818
1888888818	8111181811	1118818818	8888111818	1188888818	8811181811	1181188188	8881881181	1181188818	8818888181	1118188188	8888181818
8111188188	1888811818	8888188188	1118881811	8811118818	1188811818	8881888818	1181818111	8818881888	1181111818	8888188818	1118181811
8888181811	1111888188	8811111818	1188881881	8888181811	1118888818	8818881181	1181118818	8881888181	1181188188	8188881818	1811118818
1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22

1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984
11118111111	88881818811	18181881188	81818888888	11818111111	88181811881	18818888188	81181888888	11818111111	88188111881	1599999999984	
18111888888	81888888188	11818118811	88181811111	18181888888	81818888188	11818188811	88188111111	18818888888	81181881188	1599999999984	
81888818811	18111111111	88181888888	11818188188	81818818811	18181111111	88188188888	11818881188	81181118811	18818811111	1599999999984	
88881888188	11118188888	81818811111	18181118811	88181888188	11818188888	81181111111	18818818811	88188188188	11818888888	1599999999984	
11118181818	88881818888	18181811118	81818881818	11818181818	88181818888	18818881118	81181818181	11818181818	88188188881	1599999999984	
18111818181	81888881118	11818188881	88181818181	18181818181	81818881118	11818188881	88188181818	18818881818	81181811118	1599999999984	
81888818888	18111181818	88181881818	1181811118	81818818881	18181181818	88188181818	1181881118	81181188881	188188181818	1599999999984	
88881881118	11118181818	81818818181	18181188881	88181881118	11818181818	81181181818	18818818881	88188181118	11818818181	1599999999984	
11118111118	88881818888	18181811111	81818888881	11818111118	88181818888	18818881111	81181888881	11818111118	88188188888	1599999999984	
18111888881	81888881111	11818188888	88181811118	18181888881	81818881111	11818188888	88188111118	18818888881	81181811111	1599999999984	
81888818888	18111111118	88181888881	11818181111	81818818888	18181111118	88188188881	11818811111	81181188888	18818811118	1599999999984	
88881881111	11118188881	81818811118	18181188888	88181881111	11818188881	81181111118	18818818888	88188181111	11818888881	1599999999984	
11118111188	88881818888	18181881111	81818888811	11818111188	88181818888	18818888111	81181888811	11818111188	88188118888	1599999999984	
18111888811	81888888111	11818118888	88181811188	18181888811	81818888111	11818188888	88188111188	18818888811	81181881111	1599999999984	
81888818888	18111111188	88181888881	11818188111	81818818888	18181111188	88188188881	11818881111	81181188888	18818811188	1599999999984	
88881888111	11118188881	81818811188	18181188888	88181888111	11818188881	81181111188	18818818888	88188188111	11818888881	1599999999984	
11118111811	88881818111	18181881888	81818888188	11818111811	88181818111	18818888188	81181888188	11818111811	88188118111	1599999999984	
18111888188	81888888188	11818118111	88181811181	18181888188	81818888188	11818181111	88188111811	18818888188	81181881888	1599999999984	
81888818111	18111111811	88181888188	11818188188	81818818111	18181111811	88188188188	11818881888	81181118111	18818811811	1599999999984	
88881888188	111181888188	81818811811	18181118111	88181888188	118181888188	81181111811	18818818111	88188188188	11818888188	1599999999984	
11118111181	88881818111	18181818888	81818888818	11818111181	88181818111	18818881888	81181888818	11818111181	88188118111	1599999999984	
18111888818	81888881888	11818181111	88181811181	18181888818	81818881888	11818181111	88188111181	18818888818	81181818888	1599999999984	
81888818111	18111111811	88181888818	11818181888	81818818111	18181111811	88188188818	11818881888	81181181111	18818811181	1599999999984	
88881881888	11118188818	81818811181	18181118111	88181881888	11818188818	81181111811	18818818111	88188181888	11818888188	1599999999984	
11118118181	88881818181	18181818188	818188881818	11818118181	88181818181	188188818188	811818881818	11818181818	88188118181	1599999999984	
18111881818	818888818188	11818181811	88181811818	18181881818	818188818188	11818181811	88188111818	188188881818	81181818188	1599999999984	
81888818181	18111118181	881818881818	11818181888	81818818181	18181118181	881881881818	11818881818	81181181811	18818811818	1599999999984	
88881881888	11118188818	81818811818	18181118181	88181881888	11818188818	81181111818	18818818181	88188181888	11818888188	1599999999984	
11118118118	888818188188	18181818111	818188881881	11818118118	881818188188	18818881811	811818881881	11818181818	88188188188	1599999999984	
18111881881	81888881811	11818188188	88181811818	18181881881	81818881811	11818188188	88188111818	188188881881	81181818181	1599999999984	
818888188188	18111118118	881818881881	11818181811	818188188188	18181118118	881881881881	11818881811	81181188188	188188181818	1599999999984	
88881881811	111181881881	81818811818	18181188188	88181881811	118181881881	81181118118	188188188188	88188181811	11818881881	1599999999984	
1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984	1599999999984
23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32		

2.8 Universal Pandigital Magic Squares of Order 36

Example 8. Let's consider 81 magic squares of order 4 of type 9×9 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$	$97=(1,7)$	$113=(1,8)$	$129=(1,9)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$	$98=(2,7)$	$114=(2,8)$	$130=(2,9)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$	$99=(3,7)$	$115=(3,8)$	$131=(3,9)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$	$100=(4,7)$	$116=(4,8)$	$132=(4,9)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$	$101=(5,7)$	$117=(5,8)$	$133=(5,9)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$	$102=(6,7)$	$118=(6,8)$	$134=(6,9)$
$7=(7,1)$	$23=(7,2)$	$39=(7,3)$	$55=(7,4)$	$71=(7,5)$	$87=(7,6)$	$103=(7,7)$	$119=(7,8)$	$135=(7,9)$
$8=(8,1)$	$24=(8,2)$	$40=(8,3)$	$56=(8,4)$	$72=(8,5)$	$88=(8,6)$	$104=(8,7)$	$120=(8,8)$	$136=(8,9)$
$9=(9,1)$	$25=(9,2)$	$41=(9,3)$	$57=(9,4)$	$73=(9,5)$	$89=(9,6)$	$105=(9,7)$	$121=(9,8)$	$137=(9,9)$

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 36 with magic sum $S_{36 \times 36} := 17999999999982$. It is given below in three parts.

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$	$97=(1,7)$	$113=(1,8)$	$129=(1,9)$	$145=(1,10)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$	$98=(2,7)$	$114=(2,8)$	$130=(2,9)$	$146=(2,10)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$	$99=(3,7)$	$115=(3,8)$	$131=(3,9)$	$147=(3,10)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$	$100=(4,7)$	$116=(4,8)$	$132=(4,9)$	$148=(4,10)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$	$101=(5,7)$	$117=(5,8)$	$133=(5,9)$	$149=(5,10)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$	$102=(6,7)$	$118=(6,8)$	$134=(6,9)$	$150=(6,10)$
$7=(7,1)$	$23=(7,2)$	$39=(7,3)$	$55=(7,4)$	$71=(7,5)$	$87=(7,6)$	$103=(7,7)$	$119=(7,8)$	$135=(7,9)$	$151=(7,10)$
$8=(8,1)$	$24=(8,2)$	$40=(8,3)$	$56=(8,4)$	$72=(8,5)$	$88=(8,6)$	$104=(8,7)$	$120=(8,8)$	$136=(8,9)$	$152=(8,10)$
$9=(9,1)$	$25=(9,2)$	$41=(9,3)$	$57=(9,4)$	$73=(9,5)$	$89=(9,6)$	$105=(9,7)$	$121=(9,8)$	$137=(9,9)$	$153=(9,10)$
$10=(10,1)$	$26=(10,2)$	$42=(10,3)$	$58=(10,4)$	$74=(10,5)$	$90=(10,6)$	$106=(10,7)$	$122=(10,8)$	$138=(10,9)$	$154=(10,10)$

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 40 with magic sum $S_{40 \times 40} := 199999999999980$. It is given below in three parts.

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$	$97=(1,7)$	$113=(1,8)$	$129=(1,9)$	$145=(1,10)$	$161=(1,11)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$	$98=(2,7)$	$114=(2,8)$	$130=(2,9)$	$146=(2,10)$	$162=(2,11)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$	$99=(3,7)$	$115=(3,8)$	$131=(3,9)$	$147=(3,10)$	$163=(3,11)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$	$100=(4,7)$	$116=(4,8)$	$132=(4,9)$	$148=(4,10)$	$164=(4,11)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$	$101=(5,7)$	$117=(5,8)$	$133=(5,9)$	$149=(5,10)$	$165=(5,11)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$	$102=(6,7)$	$118=(6,8)$	$134=(6,9)$	$150=(6,10)$	$166=(6,11)$
$7=(7,1)$	$23=(7,2)$	$39=(7,3)$	$55=(7,4)$	$71=(7,5)$	$87=(7,6)$	$103=(7,7)$	$119=(7,8)$	$135=(7,9)$	$151=(7,10)$	$167=(7,11)$
$8=(8,1)$	$24=(8,2)$	$40=(8,3)$	$56=(8,4)$	$72=(8,5)$	$88=(8,6)$	$104=(8,7)$	$120=(8,8)$	$136=(8,9)$	$152=(8,10)$	$168=(8,11)$
$9=(9,1)$	$25=(9,2)$	$41=(9,3)$	$57=(9,4)$	$73=(9,5)$	$89=(9,6)$	$105=(9,7)$	$121=(9,8)$	$137=(9,9)$	$153=(9,10)$	$169=(9,11)$
$10=(10,1)$	$26=(10,2)$	$42=(10,3)$	$58=(10,4)$	$74=(10,5)$	$90=(10,6)$	$106=(10,7)$	$122=(10,8)$	$138=(10,9)$	$154=(10,10)$	$170=(10,11)$
$11=(11,1)$	$27=(11,2)$	$43=(11,3)$	$59=(11,4)$	$75=(11,5)$	$91=(11,6)$	$107=(11,7)$	$123=(11,8)$	$139=(11,9)$	$155=(11,10)$	$171=(11,11)$

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 44 with magic sum $S_{44 \times 44} := 21999999999978$. It is given below in three parts.

2.11 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 48

Example 11. Let's consider 144 magic squares of order 4 of type 12×12 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

1=(1,1)	17=(1,2)	33=(1,3)	49=(1,4)	65=(1,5)	81=(1,6)	97=(1,7)	113=(1,8)	129=(1,9)	145=(1,10)	161=(1,11)	177=(1,12)
2=(2,1)	18=(2,2)	34=(2,3)	50=(2,4)	66=(2,5)	82=(2,6)	98=(2,7)	114=(2,8)	130=(2,9)	146=(2,10)	162=(2,11)	178=(2,12)
3=(3,1)	19=(3,2)	35=(3,3)	51=(3,4)	67=(3,5)	83=(3,6)	99=(3,7)	115=(3,8)	131=(3,9)	147=(3,10)	163=(3,11)	179=(3,12)
4=(4,1)	20=(4,2)	36=(4,3)	52=(4,4)	68=(4,5)	84=(4,6)	100=(4,7)	116=(4,8)	132=(4,9)	148=(4,10)	164=(4,11)	180=(4,12)
5=(5,1)	21=(5,2)	37=(5,3)	53=(5,4)	69=(5,5)	85=(5,6)	101=(5,7)	117=(5,8)	133=(5,9)	149=(5,10)	165=(5,11)	181=(5,12)
6=(6,1)	22=(6,2)	38=(6,3)	54=(6,4)	70=(6,5)	86=(6,6)	102=(6,7)	118=(6,8)	134=(6,9)	150=(6,10)	166=(6,11)	182=(6,12)
7=(7,1)	23=(7,2)	39=(7,3)	55=(7,4)	71=(7,5)	87=(7,6)	103=(7,7)	119=(7,8)	135=(7,9)	151=(7,10)	167=(7,11)	183=(7,12)
8=(8,1)	24=(8,2)	40=(8,3)	56=(8,4)	72=(8,5)	88=(8,6)	104=(8,7)	120=(8,8)	136=(8,9)	152=(8,10)	168=(8,11)	184=(8,12)
9=(9,1)	25=(9,2)	41=(9,3)	57=(9,4)	73=(9,5)	89=(9,6)	105=(9,7)	121=(9,8)	137=(9,9)	153=(9,10)	169=(9,11)	185=(9,12)
10=(10,1)	26=(10,2)	42=(10,3)	58=(10,4)	74=(10,5)	90=(10,6)	106=(10,7)	122=(10,8)	138=(10,9)	154=(10,10)	170=(10,11)	186=(10,12)
11=(11,1)	27=(11,2)	43=(11,3)	59=(11,4)	75=(11,5)	91=(11,6)	107=(11,7)	123=(11,8)	139=(11,9)	155=(11,10)	171=(11,11)	187=(11,12)
12=(12,1)	28=(12,2)	44=(12,3)	60=(12,4)	76=(12,5)	92=(12,6)	108=(12,7)	124=(12,8)	140=(12,9)	156=(12,10)	172=(12,11)	188=(12,12)

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 48 with magic sum $S_{48 \times 48} := 23999999999976$. It is given below in three parts.

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$	$97=(1,7)$	$113=(1,8)$	$129=(1,9)$	$145=(1,10)$	$161=(1,11)$	$177=(1,12)$	$193=(1,13)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$	$98=(2,7)$	$114=(2,8)$	$130=(2,9)$	$146=(2,10)$	$162=(2,11)$	$178=(2,12)$	$194=(2,13)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$	$99=(3,7)$	$115=(3,8)$	$131=(3,9)$	$147=(3,10)$	$163=(3,11)$	$179=(3,12)$	$195=(3,13)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$	$100=(4,7)$	$116=(4,8)$	$132=(4,9)$	$148=(4,10)$	$164=(4,11)$	$180=(4,12)$	$196=(4,13)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$	$101=(5,7)$	$117=(5,8)$	$133=(5,9)$	$149=(5,10)$	$165=(5,11)$	$181=(5,12)$	$197=(5,13)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$	$102=(6,7)$	$118=(6,8)$	$134=(6,9)$	$150=(6,10)$	$166=(6,11)$	$182=(6,12)$	$198=(6,13)$
$7=(7,1)$	$23=(7,2)$	$39=(7,3)$	$55=(7,4)$	$71=(7,5)$	$87=(7,6)$	$103=(7,7)$	$119=(7,8)$	$135=(7,9)$	$151=(7,10)$	$167=(7,11)$	$183=(7,12)$	$199=(7,13)$
$8=(8,1)$	$24=(8,2)$	$40=(8,3)$	$56=(8,4)$	$72=(8,5)$	$88=(8,6)$	$104=(8,7)$	$120=(8,8)$	$136=(8,9)$	$152=(8,10)$	$168=(8,11)$	$184=(8,12)$	$200=(8,13)$
$9=(9,1)$	$25=(9,2)$	$41=(9,3)$	$57=(9,4)$	$73=(9,5)$	$89=(9,6)$	$105=(9,7)$	$121=(9,8)$	$137=(9,9)$	$153=(9,10)$	$169=(9,11)$	$185=(9,12)$	$201=(9,13)$
$10=(10,1)$	$26=(10,2)$	$42=(10,3)$	$58=(10,4)$	$74=(10,5)$	$90=(10,6)$	$106=(10,7)$	$122=(10,8)$	$138=(10,9)$	$154=(10,10)$	$170=(10,11)$	$186=(10,12)$	$202=(10,13)$
$11=(11,1)$	$27=(11,2)$	$43=(11,3)$	$59=(11,4)$	$75=(11,5)$	$91=(11,6)$	$107=(11,7)$	$123=(11,8)$	$139=(11,9)$	$155=(11,10)$	$171=(11,11)$	$187=(11,12)$	$203=(11,13)$
$12=(12,1)$	$28=(12,2)$	$44=(12,3)$	$60=(12,4)$	$76=(12,5)$	$92=(12,6)$	$108=(12,7)$	$124=(12,8)$	$140=(12,9)$	$156=(12,10)$	$172=(12,11)$	$188=(12,12)$	$204=(12,13)$
$13=(13,1)$	$29=(13,2)$	$45=(13,3)$	$61=(13,4)$	$77=(13,5)$	$93=(13,6)$	$109=(13,7)$	$125=(13,8)$	$141=(13,9)$	$157=(13,10)$	$173=(13,11)$	$189=(13,12)$	$205=(13,13)$

*In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 52 with magic sum $S_{52 \times 52} := 259999999999974$. It is given below in four parts.*

2.13 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 56

Example 13. Let's consider 196 magic squares of order 4 of type 14×14 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

1=(1,1)	17=(1,2)	33=(1,3)	49=(1,4)	65=(1,5)	81=(1,6)	97=(1,7)	113=(1,8)	129=(1,9)	145=(1,10)	161=(1,11)	177=(1,12)	193=(1,13)	193=(1,14)
2=(2,1)	18=(2,2)	34=(2,3)	50=(2,4)	66=(2,5)	82=(2,6)	98=(2,7)	114=(2,8)	130=(2,9)	146=(2,10)	162=(2,11)	178=(2,12)	194=(2,13)	193=(2,14)
3=(3,1)	19=(3,2)	35=(3,3)	51=(3,4)	67=(3,5)	83=(3,6)	99=(3,7)	115=(3,8)	131=(3,9)	147=(3,10)	163=(3,11)	179=(3,12)	195=(3,13)	193=(3,14)
4=(4,1)	20=(4,2)	36=(4,3)	52=(4,4)	68=(4,5)	84=(4,6)	100=(4,7)	116=(4,8)	132=(4,9)	148=(4,10)	164=(4,11)	180=(4,12)	196=(4,13)	193=(4,14)
5=(5,1)	21=(5,2)	37=(5,3)	53=(5,4)	69=(5,5)	85=(5,6)	101=(5,7)	117=(5,8)	133=(5,9)	149=(5,10)	165=(5,11)	181=(5,12)	197=(5,13)	193=(5,14)
6=(6,1)	22=(6,2)	38=(6,3)	54=(6,4)	70=(6,5)	86=(6,6)	102=(6,7)	118=(6,8)	134=(6,9)	150=(6,10)	166=(6,11)	182=(6,12)	198=(6,13)	193=(6,14)
7=(7,1)	23=(7,2)	39=(7,3)	55=(7,4)	71=(7,5)	87=(7,6)	103=(7,7)	119=(7,8)	135=(7,9)	151=(7,10)	167=(7,11)	183=(7,12)	199=(7,13)	193=(7,14)
8=(8,1)	24=(8,2)	40=(8,3)	56=(8,4)	72=(8,5)	88=(8,6)	104=(8,7)	120=(8,8)	136=(8,9)	152=(8,10)	168=(8,11)	184=(8,12)	200=(8,13)	193=(8,14)
9=(9,1)	25=(9,2)	41=(9,3)	57=(9,4)	73=(9,5)	89=(9,6)	105=(9,7)	121=(9,8)	137=(9,9)	153=(9,10)	169=(9,11)	185=(9,12)	201=(9,13)	193=(9,14)
10=(10,1)	26=(10,2)	42=(10,3)	58=(10,4)	74=(10,5)	90=(10,6)	106=(10,7)	122=(10,8)	138=(10,9)	154=(10,10)	170=(10,11)	186=(10,12)	202=(10,13)	193=(10,14)
11=(11,1)	27=(11,2)	43=(11,3)	59=(11,4)	75=(11,5)	91=(11,6)	107=(11,7)	123=(11,8)	139=(11,9)	155=(11,10)	171=(11,11)	187=(11,12)	203=(11,13)	193=(11,14)
12=(12,1)	28=(12,2)	44=(12,3)	60=(12,4)	76=(12,5)	92=(12,6)	108=(12,7)	124=(12,8)	140=(12,9)	156=(12,10)	172=(12,11)	188=(12,12)	204=(12,13)	193=(12,14)
13=(13,1)	29=(13,2)	45=(13,3)	61=(13,4)	77=(13,5)	93=(13,6)	109=(13,7)	125=(13,8)	141=(13,9)	157=(13,10)	173=(13,11)	189=(13,12)	205=(13,13)	193=(13,14)
14=(14,1)	30=(14,2)	46=(14,3)	62=(14,4)	78=(14,5)	94=(14,6)	110=(14,7)	126=(14,8)	142=(14,9)	158=(14,10)	174=(14,11)	190=(14,12)	206=(14,13)	193=(14,14)

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 56 with magic sum $S_{56 \times 56} := 27999999999972$. It is given below in four parts.

2.14 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 60

Example 14. Let's consider 225 magic squares of order 4 of type 15×15 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

1=(1,1)	17=(1,2)	33=(1,3)	49=(1,4)	65=(1,5)	81=(1,6)	97=(1,7)	113=(1,8)	129=(1,9)	145=(1,10)	161=(1,11)	177=(1,12)	193=(1,13)	209=(1,14)	225=(1,15)
2=(2,1)	18=(2,2)	34=(2,3)	50=(2,4)	66=(2,5)	82=(2,6)	98=(2,7)	114=(2,8)	130=(2,9)	146=(2,10)	162=(2,11)	178=(2,12)	194=(2,13)	210=(2,14)	226=(2,15)
3=(3,1)	19=(3,2)	35=(3,3)	51=(3,4)	67=(3,5)	83=(3,6)	99=(3,7)	115=(3,8)	131=(3,9)	147=(3,10)	163=(3,11)	179=(3,12)	195=(3,13)	211=(3,14)	227=(3,15)
4=(4,1)	20=(4,2)	36=(4,3)	52=(4,4)	68=(4,5)	84=(4,6)	100=(4,7)	116=(4,8)	132=(4,9)	148=(4,10)	164=(4,11)	180=(4,12)	196=(4,13)	212=(4,14)	228=(4,15)
5=(5,1)	21=(5,2)	37=(5,3)	53=(5,4)	69=(5,5)	85=(5,6)	101=(5,7)	117=(5,8)	133=(5,9)	149=(5,10)	165=(5,11)	181=(5,12)	197=(5,13)	213=(5,14)	229=(5,15)
6=(6,1)	22=(6,2)	38=(6,3)	54=(6,4)	70=(6,5)	86=(6,6)	102=(6,7)	118=(6,8)	134=(6,9)	150=(6,10)	166=(6,11)	182=(6,12)	198=(6,13)	214=(6,14)	230=(6,15)
7=(7,1)	23=(7,2)	39=(7,3)	55=(7,4)	71=(7,5)	87=(7,6)	103=(7,7)	119=(7,8)	135=(7,9)	151=(7,10)	167=(7,11)	183=(7,12)	199=(7,13)	215=(7,14)	231=(7,15)
8=(8,1)	24=(8,2)	40=(8,3)	56=(8,4)	72=(8,5)	88=(8,6)	104=(8,7)	120=(8,8)	136=(8,9)	152=(8,10)	168=(8,11)	184=(8,12)	200=(8,13)	216=(8,14)	232=(8,15)
9=(9,1)	25=(9,2)	41=(9,3)	57=(9,4)	73=(9,5)	89=(9,6)	105=(9,7)	121=(9,8)	137=(9,9)	153=(9,10)	169=(9,11)	185=(9,12)	201=(9,13)	217=(9,14)	233=(9,15)
10=(10,1)	26=(10,2)	42=(10,3)	58=(10,4)	74=(10,5)	90=(10,6)	106=(10,7)	122=(10,8)	138=(10,9)	154=(10,10)	170=(10,11)	186=(10,12)	202=(10,13)	218=(10,14)	234=(10,15)
11=(11,1)	27=(11,2)	43=(11,3)	59=(11,4)	75=(11,5)	91=(11,6)	107=(11,7)	123=(11,8)	139=(11,9)	155=(11,10)	171=(11,11)	187=(11,12)	203=(11,13)	219=(11,14)	235=(11,15)
12=(12,1)	28=(12,2)	44=(12,3)	60=(12,4)	76=(12,5)	92=(12,6)	108=(12,7)	124=(12,8)	140=(12,9)	156=(12,10)	172=(12,11)	188=(12,12)	204=(12,13)	220=(12,14)	236=(12,15)
13=(13,1)	29=(13,2)	45=(13,3)	61=(13,4)	77=(13,5)	93=(13,6)	109=(13,7)	125=(13,8)	141=(13,9)	157=(13,10)	173=(13,11)	189=(13,12)	205=(13,13)	221=(13,14)	237=(13,15)
14=(14,1)	30=(14,2)	46=(14,3)	62=(14,4)	78=(14,5)	94=(14,6)	110=(14,7)	126=(14,8)	142=(14,9)	158=(14,10)	174=(14,11)	190=(14,12)	206=(14,13)	222=(14,14)	238=(14,15)
15=(15,1)	31=(15,2)	47=(15,3)	63=(15,4)	89=(15,5)	95=(15,6)	111=(15,7)	127=(15,8)	143=(15,9)	159=(15,10)	175=(15,11)	191=(15,12)	207=(15,13)	223=(15,14)	239=(15,15)

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square of order 60 with magic sum $S_{60 \times 60} := 29999999999970$** . It is given below in four parts.

2.15 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 64

Example 15. *Let's consider all the 256 magic squares of order 4 of type 16×16 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or Figure 2.1, we have a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 64 with magic sum $S_{64 \times 64} := 319999999999968$. It is given below in four parts:*

3 Universal Magic Squares Multiples of 6

In Appendix 6 there are total 100 magic squares. All of them are universal with **magic sums** $S_{6 \times 6}^n := 2999999999997, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 100$. Let's write the Table 1.2 in the following way:

Figure 3.1.

The following subsections lead us to **universal magic squares** multiple of order 6, i.e., of orders, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36, 42, 48, 54 and 60. These are chosen according to colors appearing in the Figure 3.1. It is not the only way to write magic squares multiple of 6. The readers can chose alternative ways to write these magic squares.

3.1 Universal Magic Square of Order 12

Example 16. *Let's consider 4 magic squares of order 6 of type 2×2 given in Appendix 6 according to Table 1.2 or a part of Figure 3.1 as given below:*

$1=(1,1)$	$11=(1,2)$
$2=(2,1)$	$12=(2,2)$

*In this case, we get following **universal magic square** of order 12 with **magic sum** $S_{12 \times 12} := 5999999999994$.*

12x12-magic													599999999994
1111111111	8888188888	8811188888	1188888888	1118811111	8888811111	1181111881	8818888818	8818888818	1188188818	1181111881	88818811881	599999999994	
8888888881	1118811188	8811188881	1188811188	888111188	1111188881	8881888181	1181118188	8818888181	11881118188	88188818188	1181188181	599999999994	
8888888111	8888188111	1188881888	8811111888	1118888111	1111118888	88818881888	88188881888	11881188111	88188188111	1181181888	1181188111	599999999994	
8888881888	1118818888	1188888111	8811188111	888111888	1111188111	88818818811	11811188111	1188181888	8818881888	88188888111	118181888	599999999994	
1111111188	1118888811	8811111188	11888888811	8881888811	8888811188	1181118188	11811881811	8818818188	11881881811	88188881811	8881881888	599999999994	
1111188888	8888111111	1188811111	8811111111	1118888888	8888888888	118188818	88188811881	1188111881	8818811881	1181188818	8881888818	599999999994	
1111111811	8888188818	8811188818	1188888818	1118811811	8888811811	1181111811	88188888188	88188888188	11881888188	1181111811	88818811811	599999999994	
8888888188	1118818111	8811188188	1188818111	8881118111	1111188188	88818881888	1181118111	88188881888	11881118111	88188818111	1181881888	599999999994	
8888888188	8888188188	1188881881	8811118811	1118888188	1111118811	88818888188	88188888188	11881118811	88188188111	1181188188	1181118811	599999999994	
8888881881	1118818811	1188888188	8811188188	8881118811	1111188188	88818818811	1181118811	1188188188	8818888188	88188818811	118188188	599999999994	
1111118111	1118888188	8811118111	1188888188	888188188	8888818111	1181118111	1181188188	8818818111	1188188188	8818888188	88818818111	599999999994	
1111188188	8888111811	1188811811	8811111811	1118888188	8888888818	1181888188	88188811811	1188111811	8818811811	1181188818	8881888818	599999999994	
599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	599999999994	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		

3.2 Universal Magic Square of Order 18

Example 17. Let's consider 9 magic squares of order 6 of type 3×3 given in Appendix 6 according to Table 1.2 or a part of Figure 3.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$11=(1,2)$	$21=(1,3)$
$2=(2,1)$	$12=(2,2)$	$22=(2,3)$
$3=(3,1)$	$13=(3,2)$	$23=(3,3)$

In this case, we get following **universal magic square** of order 18 with magic sum $S_{18 \times 18} := 8999999999991$. It is given in below in two parts

18x18-magic								
1111111111	8888188888	8811188888	1188888888	1118811111	8888811111	1181111881	8818888818	8818888818
8888888881	1118811188	8811188881	1188881118	8888111188	1111888811	8881888818	1181111818	8818888181
8888888111	8888188111	1188881888	8811111888	1118888111	1111118888	8881888188	8818888188	1188118811
8888881888	1118818888	1188888111	8811188111	8888111888	1111881111	8881881881	1181118811	1188181888
1111111188	1118888881	8811111188	1188888881	8888188881	8888881188	1181118188	1181188181	8818818188
1111188888	8888111111	1188881111	8811111111	1118888888	8888888888	118188818	88188811881	1188111881
1111111811	8888188818	8811188818	1188888818	1118811811	8888881181	118111811	8818888818	8818888818
8888888188	1118818111	8811188188	1188881811	8888111811	1111881888	8881888188	1181118111	8818888188
8888888188	8888188188	1188881881	8811111881	1118888188	1111118811	8881888188	8818888188	1188111881
8888881881	1118818811	1188888188	8811188188	8888111881	111188188	8881881881	1181118811	1188188188
1111118111	1118888188	8811111811	1188888188	8888188188	8888881811	1181118111	1181188188	8818818111
1111188188	8888111811	1188881181	8811111811	1118888188	8888888818	1181888188	8818881181	1188111811
1111118118	8888188188	8811188188	1188888188	1118818118	8888881818	1181118118	8818888188	8818888188
8888881811	1118818818	8811181811	1188881888	8888118818	111181811	8881888181	1181118818	8818881811
8888881118	8888181118	1188881888	8811118888	1118881118	1111118888	8881888118	8818888118	1188118888
8888881888	1118818888	1188881118	8811181118	8888118888	111181118	8881881888	1181118888	1188181118
1111188188	1118881811	8811118818	1188881811	8888181811	8888881888	1181188188	1181181811	8818818818
1111188188	8888111818	1188881818	8811111818	1118888188	8888888818	1181888188	8818881181	1188111818
8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999

									8999999999
1188188818	1181111881	8881881188	1181811111	8181888888	8111888888	18888188888	18818811111	88188111111	8999999999
1188111818	8818881818	1181881811	8818818881	1881881118	8111888881	18888111188	8181111188	1181888881	8999999999
8818818811	1181181888	1181188111	8818818811	8181881111	18888118888	8111818888	18818888111	1181818888	8999999999
8818881888	8818881881	1181818888	8818811888	1881881888	18888188111	8111888111	8181118888	1181888111	8999999999
1188188181	8818888181	8881881818	1181811188	1881888881	8111811188	18888188881	8181888811	88188111188	8999999999
8818811881	1181188818	8881888818	1181888888	8181111111	18888111111	8111811111	18818888888	88188188888	8999999999
1188188818	1181111811	8881881181	1181811811	8181888188	8111888818	18888188818	18818811811	88188111811	8999999999
1188111811	8818881811	1181881888	8818818888	1881881811	8111888188	18888118111	8181118111	11818881888	8999999999
8818818811	1181188188	1181118811	8818818818	818188188	18888118811	8111818881	18818888188	1181818881	8999999999
8818888188	8818881881	118188188	8818811881	1881881881	18888188188	8111888188	8181118811	1181888188	8999999999
1188188188	8818888188	8881881811	1181818111	18818888188	8111818111	18888188188	8181881888	8818811811	8999999999
8818811811	1181188818	8881888818	1181888818	8181111811	18888111811	8111811811	18818888188	8818818888	8999999999
1188188188	1181111818	8881881818	118181818	8181881881	81118881881	18888188188	1881881818	8818811818	8999999999
1188118818	8818881888	1181818181	8818818181	1881881888	8111881811	18888188188	8181188188	1181881811	8999999999
8818818888	1181181118	1181118888	8818818118	8181811118	18888188881	8111818888	18818881118	1181818888	8999999999
8818881118	8818881888	118181118	8818818888	1881881888	18888181118	8111881118	818118888	1181881118	8999999999
1188181811	8818888181	8881881888	1181818818	1881888181	81118188188	18888181811	8181818181	88188188188	8999999999
881881818	1181188188	8881888818	1181888188	818111818	1888811818	811181818	1881888818	8818818818	8999999999
8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999	8999999999

3.3 Universal Magic Square of Order 24

Example 18. Let's consider 16 magic squares of order 6 of type 4×4 given in Appendix 6 according to Table 1.2 or a part of Figure 3.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$11=(1,2)$	$21=(1,3)$	$31=(1,4)$
$2=(2,1)$	$12=(2,2)$	$22=(2,3)$	$32=(2,4)$
$3=(3,1)$	$13=(3,2)$	$23=(3,3)$	$33=(3,4)$
$4=(4,1)$	$14=(4,2)$	$24=(4,3)$	$34=(4,4)$

In this case, we get following **universal magic square** of order 24 with magic sum $S_{24 \times 24} := 11999999999988$. It is given in below in two parts

24x24-magic												
1111111111	8888188888	8811188888	1188888888	1118811111	8888811111	1118111188	8818888818	8818888818	1188188818	1181111188	8881881188	
8888888881	1118811188	8811188881	1188811188	8888111188	1111188881	8881888818	1181118188	8818888181	1188118188	8818881818	1181881811	
8888888111	8888188111	1188881888	8811118888	1118888111	1111118888	8881888188	8818888188	1188118811	8818818811	1181181888	1181188111	
8888818888	1118818888	1188888111	8811188111	8888118888	1111188111	8881881881	1181118811	1188181888	8818881888	8818881881	1181818888	
1111111188	1118888811	8811111188	1188888811	8888188811	8888811188	1118111818	1181188181	8818818188	1188188181	8818888181	8881881818	
1111188888	8888111111	1188881111	8811111111	1118888888	8888888888	1118188818	8818881188	1188111881	8818811881	1181188818	8881888818	
1111111811	8888188818	8811188818	1188888818	1118811811	8888811811	1118111811	8818888818	8818888818	1188188818	1181111811	8881881181	
8888888188	1118818111	8811188188	1188818111	8888118111	1111188188	8881888188	1181118111	8818888188	1188118111	8818881811	1181881888	
8888888188	8888188188	1188881881	8811118811	1118888188	1111118811	8881888188	8818888188	1188118811	8818818811	1181188188	1181118811	
8888818811	1118818811	1188888188	8811188188	8888118811	1111188188	8881881881	1181118811	1188188188	8818888188	8818881881	1181881888	
1111118111	1118888188	8811118111	1188888188	8888188188	8888818111	1118111811	1181188188	8818818111	1188188188	8818888188	8881881811	
1111188818	8888111811	1188881181	8811111811	1118888818	8888888818	1118188818	8818881181	1188111811	8818811811	1181188818	8881888818	
1111118118	8888188188	8811188188	1188888188	1118818118	8888818118	1118111818	8818888881	8818888881	1188188188	1181118118	8881881818	
8888881811	1118818818	8811181811	1188818818	8888118818	1111181811	8881888181	1181118818	8818881811	1188118818	8818881888	1181818111	
8888881118	8888181118	1188881888	8811118888	1118881118	1111118888	8881888118	8818888118	1188118888	8818818888	1181181118	1181188881	
8888818888	1118818888	1188888118	8811181118	8888118888	1111181118	8881881888	1181118888	1188181118	8818888118	8818881888	1181811118	
1111118818	1118881811	8811118818	1188888181	8888181811	8888818818	1118118818	1181181811	8818818818	1188181811	8818888181	8881881888	
1111188188	8888111818	1188881818	8811111818	1118888881	8888888881	1118188188	8818881818	1188111818	8818818188	1181188188	8881888188	
1111118118	8888181888	8811181888	1188888188	1118818118	8888818118	1118118118	8818888888	8818888888	1188181888	1181118118	8881881818	
8888881818	11188181818	8811181818	1188881818	88881181818	1111181818	88818881818	11811181818	8818881818	11881181818	8818881818	1181818181	
8888881181	8888181181	1188881888	8811118888	1118881181	1111118888	8881888118	8818888118	1188118888	8818818888	1181181181	1181188888	
8888818888	1118818888	1188888118	8811181118	8888118888	1111181118	8881881888	1181118888	1188181118	8818888118	8818881888	1181811118	
1111118818	1118881811	8811118818	1188888181	8888181811	8888818818	1118118818	1181181811	8818818818	1188181811	8818888181	8881881888	
1111188188	8888111818	1188881818	8811111818	1118888881	8888888881	1118188188	8818881818	1188111818	8818818188	1181188188	8881888188	
1111118118	8888181888	8811181888	1188888188	1118818118	8888818118	1118118118	8818888888	8818888888	1188181888	1181118118	8881881818	
8888881818	11188181818	8811181818	1188881818	88881181818	1111181818	88818881818	11811181818	8818881818	11881181818	8818881818	1181818181	
8888881181	8888181181	1188881888	8811118888	1118881181	1111118888	8881888118	8818888118	1188118888	8818818888	1181181181	1181188888	
8888818888	1118818888	1188888118	8811181118	8888118888	1111181118	8881881888	1181118888	1188181118	8818888118	8818881888	1181811118	
11111181818	1118881818	88111181818	11888881818	8888181818	88888181818	11181181818	1181181818	88188181818	1188181818	88188881818	8881881818	
1111181888	8888118118	1188881818	8811118118	1118888881	8888888881	1118181888	8818881818	1188111818	8818818188	1181181888	8881888188	
119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	

												1199999999988
1181811111	8181888888	8111888888	18888188888	18818811111	88188111111	18118111111	81818188888	81181888888	18881888888	18181811111	81888111111	1199999999988
88188188881	18818811188	81118888811	18888111188	81811111888	11818888811	81888188881	18181811188	81181888811	18881811188	81818111888	18118888811	1199999999988
88188188111	81818811111	18888118888	81118188888	18818888111	11818188888	81888188111	18181888111	18881818888	81181188888	18181888111	18118188888	1199999999988
88188118888	18818818888	18888188111	81118881111	81811188888	11818881111	81888118888	18181818888	18881888111	81181881111	81818188888	18118881111	1199999999988
11818111888	18818888811	81118111888	18888188811	81818888111	88188111888	18118111888	18181888811	81181118888	18881888811	81818188811	81888111888	1199999999988
11818888888	81811111111	18888111111	81118111111	18818888888	88188188888	18118888888	81818111111	18881811111	81181111111	18181888888	81888188888	1199999999988
11818118181	8181888188	81118888188	188881888188	188188118181	881881118181	18118118181	818181888188	81181888188	18881888188	181818118181	818881118181	1199999999988
881881881888	18818818111	81118881888	18888118111	81811181111	11818881888	818881881888	18181818111	81181881888	18881818111	81818118111	18118881888	1199999999988
88188188188	818188188	18888118811	81118188111	18818888188	11818188111	81888188188	18181888188	18881818811	81181188111	18181888188	18118188111	1199999999988
88188118811	18818818811	18888188188	8111888188	81811188111	1181888188	81888118811	18181818811	18881888188	8118188188	81818118811	1811888188	1199999999988
11818181811	18818881888	81118181811	188881881888	81818818888	88188118111	18118181811	181818881888	81181181811	188818881888	818181881888	81888118111	1199999999988
11818888188	81811118111	18888111811	81118118111	18818888188	881881888188	18118888188	81818111811	18881811811	81181118111	181818888188	818881888188	1199999999988
11818181818	81818881881	81118881881	188881881881	18818818118	88188118118	18118181818	8181818881881	811818881881	188818881881	18181818118	81888118118	1199999999988
881881818181	188188188188	811188818181	18888188188	81811188188	118188818181	818881818181	181818188188	81181818181	188818188188	81818188188	181188818181	1199999999988
88188181118	81818181118	18888188881	81118188881	18818881118	11818188881	81888181118	18181818118	188818188881	81181188881	18181881118	18118188881	1199999999988
88188188881	188188188881	18888181118	81118881118	81811188881	11818881118	81888188881	181818188881	18881881118	8118181118	81818188881	18118881118	1199999999988
11818188188	18818881811	81118188188	18888181811	81818181811	88188188188	18118188188	18181881811	81181188188	18881881811	81818181811	81888188188	1199999999988
11818881881	81811181818	1888811818	81118181818	188188881881	881881881881	18118881881	8181811818	1888181818	81181181818	181818881881	818881881881	1199999999988
11818181818	81818188881	811188818881	188881818881	18818818118	8818818118	18118181818	81818188881	8118188881	188818818881	18181818118	8188818118	1199999999988
881881818181	188188181818	811188818181	18888181818	81811181818	118188818181	818881818181	181818181818	81181818181	188818181818	81818181818	181188818181	1199999999988
88188181181	81818181181	18888188818	81118188818	18818881181	11818188818	81888181181	181818181181	188818188818	81181188818	18181881181	18118188818	1199999999988
88188188818	188188188818	18888181181	81118881181	81811188818	11818881181	81888188818	181818188818	18881881181	8118181181	81818188818	18118881181	1199999999988
11818181818	188188818181	81118181818	188881818181	818181818181	88188181818	18118181818	181818818181	81181181818	188818818181	818181818181	81888181818	1199999999988
11818818881	81811181118	18888181118	81118181118	188188818881	881881818881	18118818881	81818181118	18881818118	81181181118	181818818881	818881818881	1199999999988
1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988	1199999999988
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	

3.4 Universal Magic Square of Order 30

Example 19. Let's consider 25 magic squares of order 6 of type 5×5 given in Appendix 6 according to Table 1.2 or a part of Figure 3.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$11=(1,2)$	$21=(1,3)$	$31=(1,4)$	$41=(1,5)$
$2=(2,1)$	$12=(2,2)$	$22=(2,3)$	$32=(2,4)$	$42=(2,5)$
$3=(3,1)$	$13=(3,2)$	$23=(3,3)$	$33=(3,4)$	$43=(3,5)$
$4=(4,1)$	$14=(4,2)$	$24=(4,3)$	$34=(4,4)$	$44=(4,5)$
$5=(5,1)$	$15=(5,2)$	$25=(5,3)$	$35=(5,4)$	$45=(5,5)$

In this case, we get a **universal magic square** of order 30 with magic sum $S_{30 \times 30} := 1499999999985$. It is given below in three parts.

30x30-magic									
1111111111	888811888888	881111888888	118888888888	1118811111	888888111111	11181111881	881888888118	881188888118	118811888118
888888888811	111188111188	881111888811	118888111188	888811111888	111111888811	888188881811	11811118188	881188881811	11881118188
888888881111	888811881111	118888118888	881111118888	111188881111	111111118888	888188811888	881888811888	118811188111	881188188111
888888118888	111188118888	118888881111	881111881111	888811118888	111111881111	888188188111	118111188111	118811811888	881188811888
111111111888	111188888811	881111111888	118888888811	888811888811	888888111188	11181118188	118111881811	881188118188	118811881811
111111888888	888811111111	118888111111	881111111111	111188888888	888888888888	111811888118	881888111881	11881111881	881188111881
11111111811	888811888188	881111888188	118888888188	11118811811	888888111811	11181111811	881888888188	881188888188	118811888188
888888881888	111188118111	881111881888	118888118111	888811118111	111111881888	888188881888	11811118111	881188881888	11881118111
888888881188	888811881188	118888118811	881111118811	111188881188	111111118811	888188881188	881888881188	118811118811	881188118811
888888118811	111188118811	118888881188	881111881188	888811118811	111111881188	888188118811	11811118811	118811881188	881188881188
11111118111	111188881888	881111118111	118888881888	888811881888	888888118111	11181118111	118111881888	881188118111	118811881888
111111888188	88881111811	118888111811	88111111811	111188888188	888888888188	111811888188	881888111811	11881111811	881188111811
11111118118	888811881881	881111881881	118888881881	111188118118	888888118118	11181118118	8818888881881	881188881881	118811881881
888888811811	111188188188	881111811811	118888188188	888811188188	111111811811	888188811811	118111188188	881188811811	118811188188
888888811118	888811811118	118888188881	881111188881	111188811118	111111188881	888188811118	881888811118	118811188881	881188188881
888888188881	111188188881	118888811118	881111811118	888811188881	111111811118	888188188881	118111188881	118811811118	881188811118
11111188188	111188811811	881111188188	118888811811	888811811811	888888188188	111811188188	118111811811	881188188188	118811811811
111111881881	88881118118	118888118118	88111118118	111188881881	8888888881881	111811881881	881888118118	11881118118	881188118118
11111181118	888811818881	881111818881	118888818881	111188181118	888888181118	111811181118	881888818881	881188818881	118811818881
888888818181	111188181818	881111818181	118888181818	888811181818	111111818181	888188818181	118111181818	881188818181	118811181818
888888811181	888811811181	118888188818	881111188818	111188811181	111111188818	888188811181	881888811181	118811188818	881188188818
888888188818	111188188818	118888811181	881111811181	888811188818	111111811181	888188188818	118111188818	118811811181	881188811181
11111181818	111188818181	881111181818	118888818181	888811818181	888888181818	111811181818	118111818181	881188181818	118811818181
111111818881	888811181118	118888181118	881111181118	111188818881	888888818881	111811818881	881888181118	118811181118	881188181118
11111111181	888811888818	881111888818	118888888818	111188111181	888888111181	11181111181	881888888818	881188888818	118811888818
888888818888	111188181111	881111818888	118888181111	888811181111	111111818888	888188818888	118111181111	881188818888	118811181111
888888818818	888811818818	118888181181	881111181181	111188818818	111111181181	888188818818	881888818818	118811181181	881188181181
888888181181	111188181181	118888818818	881111818818	888811181181	111111818818	888188181181	118111181181	118811818818	881188818818
11111181111	111188818888	881111181111	118888818888	888811818888	888888181111	111811181111	118111818888	881188181111	118811818888
111111888818	88881111181	118888111181	88111111181	111188888818	888888888818	111811888818	881888111181	11881111181	881188111181
1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

11811111881	888188111881	118118111111	811811888888	811118888888	188881888888	188188111111	881881111111	181118111111	818181888888
881888118188	111811881811	881881888811	188188111188	811118888811	188881111188	811811111188	118118888811	818881888811	181818111188
118111811888	111811188111	881881881111	811811881111	188881118888	811118118888	188188881111	118118118888	818881881111	818181881111
881888188111	111811811888	881881118888	188188118888	188881881111	811118881111	811811118888	118118881111	818881118888	181818118888
881888881811	888188118188	118118111188	188188888811	811118111188	188881888811	811811888811	881881111188	181118111188	181818888811
118111888118	888188888118	118118888888	811811111111	188881111111	811118111111	188188888888	881881888888	181118888888	818181111111
11811111811	888188111811	118118111811	811811888188	811118888188	188881888188	188188111811	881881111811	181118111811	818181888188
881888118111	111811881888	881881881888	188188118111	811118881888	188881118111	811811118111	118118881888	818881881888	181818118111
118111881188	111811188111	881881881188	811811881188	188881118811	811118118811	188188881188	118118118811	818881881188	818181881188
881888118811	111811881188	881881118811	188188118811	188881881188	811118881188	811811118811	118118881188	818881118811	181818118811
881888881888	888188118111	118118118111	188188881888	811118118111	188881881888	811811881888	881881118111	181118118111	181818881888
118111888188	888188888188	118118888188	811811111811	188881111811	811118111811	188188888188	881881888188	181118888188	818181111811
118111118118	888188118118	118118118118	811811881881	811118881881	188881881881	188188118118	881881118118	181118118118	818181881881
881888188188	111811811811	881881811811	188188188188	811118811811	188881188188	81181188188	118118811811	818881811811	181818188188
118111811118	111811188881	881881811118	811811811118	188881188881	8111181188881	188188811118	118118188881	818881811118	818181811118
881888188881	111811811118	881881188881	188188188881	188881811118	811118811118	81181188881	118118811118	818881188881	181818188881
881888811811	888188188188	118118188188	188188811811	811118188188	188881811811	811811811811	88188188188	181118188188	181818811811
118111881881	8881888881881	118118881881	811811118118	188881118118	811118118118	1881888881881	881881881881	181118881881	818181118118
118111181118	888188181118	118118181118	811811818881	811118818881	188881818881	188188181118	88188181118	181118181118	818181818881
881888181818	111811818181	881881818181	188188181818	811118818181	188881181818	811811181818	118118818181	818881818181	181818181818
118111811181	111811188818	881881811181	811811811181	188881188818	8111181188818	188188811181	118118188818	818881811181	818181811181
881888188818	111811811181	881881188818	188188188818	188881811181	811118811181	81181188818	118118811181	818881188818	181818188818
881888818181	888188181818	118118181818	188188818181	811118181818	188881818181	811811818181	88188181818	181118181818	181818818181
118111818881	888188818881	118118818881	811811181118	188881181118	811118181118	188188818881	881881818881	181118818881	818181181118
118111111181	888188111181	118118111181	811811888818	811118888818	188881888818	188188111181	881881111181	181118111181	818181888818
881888181111	111811818888	881881818888	188188181111	811118818888	188881181111	811811181111	118118818888	818881818888	181818181111
118111818818	111811181181	881881818818	811811818818	188881181181	811118181181	188188818818	118118181181	818881818818	818181818818
881888181181	111811818818	881881181181	188188181181	188881818818	811118818818	811811181181	118118818818	818881181181	181818181181
881888818888	888188181111	118118181111	188188818888	811118181111	188881818888	811811818888	881881811111	181118181111	181818818888
118111888818	88818888818	118118888818	811811111181	188881111181	811118111181	18818888818	881881888818	181118888818	818181111181
1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20

										1499999999985
81181888888	18881888888	18181811111	81888111111	11181111111	81888888888	81881888888	18181888888	18111111111	88881811111	1499999999985
81181888811	18881811188	81818111188	18118888811	88881888811	18111111188	81881888811	18181111188	81888111188	11181888811	1499999999985
18881818888	81181118888	18181888111	18118188888	88881888111	81888881111	18181118888	81881818888	18111881111	11181118888	1499999999985
18881888111	81181881111	81818118888	18118881111	88881818888	18111118888	18181881111	81881888111	81888118888	11181881111	1499999999985
81181111188	18881888811	81818188811	81888111188	11181111188	18111888811	81881811188	18181888811	81888888811	88881811188	1499999999985
18881811111	81181111111	18181888888	81888188888	11181888888	81888111111	18181111111	81881811111	18111888888	88881888888	1499999999985
81181888188	18881888188	18181811811	81888111811	11181118111	81888888188	81881888188	18181888188	18111118111	88881811811	1499999999985
81181881888	18881818111	81818118111	18118881888	88881888188	18111118111	81881888188	18181118111	81888118111	11181881888	1499999999985
18881818811	81181118811	18181888188	18118188811	88881888188	81888881888	18181118811	81881818811	18111881888	11181118811	1499999999985
18881888188	81181881888	81818118811	18118881888	88881818811	18111118811	18181881888	81881888188	81888118811	11181881888	1499999999985
81181118111	188818881888	818181881888	818881118111	11181118111	18111881888	81881811811	18181881888	81888881888	88881811811	1499999999985
18881811811	81181118111	181818888188	818881888188	11181888188	81888111811	18181118111	81881811811	18111888188	88881888188	1499999999985
81181881881	188818881881	18181818118	81888111818	11181118118	818888881881	818818881881	18181881881	18111118118	88881811818	1499999999985
81181818111	188818188188	81818188188	18118881811	88881881811	18111188188	81881881811	18181188188	81888188188	11181818111	1499999999985
18881818881	81181188881	18181881118	18118188881	88881881118	81888881118	18181188881	81881818881	1811181118	11181188881	1499999999985
18881881118	8118181118	81818188881	18118881118	88881818881	18111188881	1818181118	81881881118	81888188881	1118181118	1499999999985
81181881888	18881881811	81818181811	81888188188	11181881888	18111818111	81881818111	18181818111	81888881811	88881818188	1499999999985
18881818118	8118118118	181818881881	818881881881	11181881881	81888818118	1818118118	81881818118	18111881881	888818881881	1499999999985
81181818881	188818818881	18181818118	81888118118	11181118118	818888818881	818818818881	18181818881	1811118118	88881818118	1499999999985
81181818181	188818181818	81818181818	181188818181	888818818181	18111181818	818818818181	18181181818	81888181818	11181818181	1499999999985
188818188818	81181188818	181818811181	18118188818	888818811181	818888811181	18181188818	81881818818	18111811181	11181188818	1499999999985
188818811181	81181811181	81818188818	181188811181	888818188818	18111188818	18181811181	818818811181	81888188818	11181811181	1499999999985
811818181818	188818818181	818181818181	818881181818	11181181818	18111818181	818818181818	18181818181	818888818181	888818181818	1499999999985
18881818118	8118118118	181818881881	81888181881	11181818881	81888818118	1818118118	81881818118	18111818881	88881881881	1499999999985
81181888818	18881888818	18181811181	81888111181	1118111181	81888888818	81881888818	18181888818	1811111181	88881811181	1499999999985
81181818888	18881818111	81818181111	181188818888	888818818888	18111181111	818818818888	18181811111	81888181111	11181818888	1499999999985
188818181181	81181181181	181818818818	18118181181	888818818818	818888818818	18181181181	818818181181	18111818818	11181181181	1499999999985
188818818818	81181818818	818181818181	181188818818	888818181181	18111181181	18181818818	818818818818	81888181181	11181818818	1499999999985
81181811111	188818818888	818181818888	818881181111	11181181111	18111818888	81881811111	18181818888	818888818888	88881811111	1499999999985
18881811181	8118111181	18181888818	81888188818	11181888818	81888811181	1818111181	81881811181	18111888818	88881888818	1499999999985
1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985	1499999999985
21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	

3.5 Universal Magic Square of Order 36

Example 20. Let's consider 36 magic squares of order 6 of type 6×6 given in Appendix 6 according to Table 1.2 or a part of Figure 3.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$11=(1,2)$	$21=(1,3)$	$31=(1,4)$	$41=(1,5)$	$51=(1,6)$
$2=(2,1)$	$12=(2,2)$	$22=(2,3)$	$32=(2,4)$	$42=(2,5)$	$52=(2,6)$
$3=(3,1)$	$13=(3,2)$	$23=(3,3)$	$33=(3,4)$	$43=(3,5)$	$53=(3,6)$
$4=(4,1)$	$14=(4,2)$	$24=(4,3)$	$34=(4,4)$	$44=(4,5)$	$54=(4,6)$
$5=(5,1)$	$15=(5,2)$	$25=(5,3)$	$35=(5,4)$	$45=(5,5)$	$55=(5,6)$
$6=(6,1)$	$16=(6,2)$	$26=(6,3)$	$36=(6,4)$	$46=(6,5)$	$56=(6,6)$

In this case, we get a **universal magic square** of order 36 with magic sum $S_{36 \times 36} := 179999999999982$. It is given below in three parts.

36x36-magic												
1111111111	8888188888	8811188888	1188888888	1118811111	8888811111	1181111881	8818888818	8818888818	1188188818	1181111881	88818811881	
8888888881	1118811188	8811188881	1188811188	8888111188	1111188881	88818888181	11811118188	88188888181	11881118188	88188818188	11811881811	
8888888111	8888188111	1188881888	8811111888	1118888111	1111118888	88818881888	88188881888	11881188111	88188188111	1181181888	1181188111	
88888818888	1118818888	1188888111	8811188111	88881118888	1111188111	88818818811	11811188111	1188181888	8818881888	88188818811	1181818888	
1111111188	1118888881	8811111188	1188888881	8888188881	8888811188	1181118188	11811881811	8818818188	11881881811	88188888181	88818818188	
1111188888	8888111111	1188881111	8811111111	1118888888	8888888888	118188818	88188811881	1188111881	88188811881	1181188818	8881888818	
1111111811	8888188818	8811188818	1188888818	1118811811	8888811811	118111811	88188888188	88188888188	11881888188	1181111811	88818811811	
88888881888	1118818111	88111881888	11888818111	88881118111	11111881888	88818888188	11811118111	88188881888	11881118111	88188818111	1181881888	
8888888188	8888188188	11888818811	88111118811	1118888188	1111118811	88818888188	88188888188	11881118811	88188188111	1181188188	1181118811	
88888818811	1118818811	11888888188	8811188188	88881118811	1111188188	88818818811	11811118811	1188188188	88188888188	88188818811	118188188	
1111118111	11188881888	88111118111	11888881888	88881881888	8888818111	1181118111	11811881888	8818818111	11881881888	88188888888	88818818111	
11111888188	88881111811	11888811811	88111111811	11188888188	88888888188	1181888188	88188811811	1188111811	88188811811	11811888188	88818888188	
1111118118	88881881881	88111881881	118888881881	1118818118	8888818118	1181118118	881888881881	881888881881	11881881881	1181118118	88818818118	
88888881811	11188188188	88111818111	118888188188	88881188188	11111818111	88818881811	11811188188	88188881811	11881188188	881888188188	1181818111	
88888881118	8888181118	118888188881	881111188881	1118881118	11111188881	88818881118	88188881118	11881188881	881888188881	1181181118	11811188881	
888888188881	111888188881	11888881118	8811181118	88881188881	1111181118	888188188881	11811188881	1188181118	88188881118	881888188881	118181118	
11111188188	1118881811	88111188188	11888881811	8888181811	888888188188	1181188188	1181181811	88188188188	1188181811	88188881811	888188188188	
11111881881	88881118118	11888818118	88111118118	1118888881	888888881881	1181881881	88188818118	11881118118	88188818118	11811881881	8881888881	
1111118118	88881818881	88111818881	11888888881	1118818118	88888818118	1181118118	88188888881	8818888881	11881818881	1181118118	88818818118	
888888818181	11188181818	88111818181	118888181818	88881181818	11111818181	888188818181	11811181818	881888818181	11881181818	881888181818	118181818181	
88888881181	8888181181	118888188818	88111188818	1118881181	11111188818	88818881181	88188881181	11881188818	881888188818	1181181181	11811188818	
888888188818	111888188818	11888881181	8811181181	88881188818	1111181181	888188188818	11811188818	1188181181	88188881181	881888188818	118181181	
11111181818	11188818181	88111181818	118888818181	88881818181	888888181818	1181181818	11811818181	88188188188	11881818181	881888818181	888188181818	
11111818881	8888118118	11888818118	8811118118	11188818881	88888888881	11818188881	881888818118	1188118118	88188818118	11811818881	88818888881	
1111111181	88881888818	88111888818	118888888818	1118811181	88888811181	1181111181	881888888818	88188888818	11881888818	1181111181	88818811181	
888888818888	11188181111	88111818888	118888181111	88881181111	11111818888	888188818888	11811181111	881888818888	11881181111	881888181111	11818188888	
888888818818	88881818818	11888818181	881111818181	11188818818	111111818181	888188818818	881888818818	118811818181	8818881818181	11811818818	118111818181	
88888818181	111881818181	11888888818	88111818818	888811818181	11111818818	8881881818181	118111818181	11881818818	88188888818	8818881818181	11818188818	
11111181111	11188818888	88111181111	118888818888	88881818888	888888181111	11811181111	11811818888	88188181111	11881818888	881888818888	888188181111	
11111888818	88881111181	118888111181	88111111181	11188888818	888888888818	1181888818	88188811181	11881111181	88188811181	11811888818	88818888818	
1111111888	88881888111	88111888111	118888888111	1118811888	88888811888	1181111888	881888888111	88188888111	11881888111	1181111888	88818811888	
88888888118	1118818881	8811188118	11888818881	88881118881	1111188118	88818888118	11811118881	8818888118	11881118881	88188818881	118188118	
88888881188	8888181188	118888188811	88111188811	1118881188	11111188811	888188881188	88188881188	11881188811	881888188811	1181181188	11811188811	
888888188811	11188188811	11888881188	8811181188	88881188811	1111181188	888188188811	11811188811	1188181188	88188881188	881888188811	118181188	
11111118881	1118888118	88111118881	11888888118	8888188118	88888818881	11811118881	1181188118	8818818881	1188188118	88188888118	88818818881	
11111888111	88881111888	11888811888	88111111888	11188888111	888888888111	1181888111	88188811888	11881111888	88188811888	11811888111	888188888111	
1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	

11811811111	81181188888	81111888888	18888188888	18818811111	88188111111	18118111111	81818188888	81118188888	18881888888	18181111111	81888111111
88188188881	18818811118	81111888881	18888111118	81181111118	11811888881	81888188881	18181111118	81118188881	18881811118	81818111118	18111888881
88188188111	81181188111	18888111888	81111811888	18818881111	11811811888	81888188111	81818188111	18881811888	81118111888	18181881111	18111811888
88188111888	18818811888	18888188111	81111888111	81181111888	11811888111	81888111888	18181111888	18881881111	81118188111	81818111888	18111888111
11818111118	18818888881	81111811118	18888188881	81181188881	88188111118	18118111118	18181888881	81118111118	18881888881	81818188881	81888111118
11811888888	81181111111	18888111111	81111811111	18818888888	88188188888	18118888888	81818111111	18881811111	81118111111	18181888888	81888188888
11818111811	81181188818	81111888818	18888188818	18818811811	88188111811	18118111811	81818188818	81118188818	18881888818	18181111811	81888111811
88188188188	18818811811	81111888188	18888118111	81181118111	11811888188	81888188188	18181181111	81118188188	18881811811	81818118111	18111888188
88188188118	81181188118	18888118811	81111811881	18818881188	11811811881	81888188118	81818188118	18881811881	81118111881	18181881188	18111811881
88188111881	18818811881	18888188118	81111888188	81181111881	11811888188	81888111881	18181188111	18881888118	81118188188	81818111881	18111888188
11818118111	18818888188	81111811811	18888188188	81181188188	88188118111	18118118111	18181888188	81118118111	18881888188	81818188188	81888118111
11811888818	81181111811	18888111811	81111811811	18818888818	88188188818	18118888818	81818111811	18881811811	81118111811	18181888818	81888188818
11811811818	81181188188	81111888188	18888188188	18818811818	88188111818	18118111818	81818188188	81118188188	18881888188	18181111818	81888111818
88188181181	18818818818	81111881811	18888188188	81181188188	11811881811	81888181181	18181881888	81118181811	18881818818	81818188188	18111881811
88188181118	81181181118	18888188881	81111818888	18818881118	11811818888	81888181118	81818181118	18881818888	81118118888	18181881118	18111818888
88188188881	18818818888	18888181118	81111881118	81181118888	11811881118	81888188881	18181888881	18881881118	81118181118	81818188881	18111881118
11811818818	18818881811	81111818818	18888181811	81181181811	88188188188	18118188188	18181881811	81118188188	18881881811	81818181811	81888188188
11811888188	81181118118	18888118118	81111811818	18818888818	88188188188	18118888818	81818118118	18881811818	81118111818	18181888818	81888188188
11811811818	81181188881	81111888881	18888181888	18818811818	88188111818	18118111818	81818188881	81118188881	18881888881	18181881188	81888111818
88188181818	18818818818	81111881818	18888181818	81181181818	11811881818	81888181818	18181818818	81118181818	18881818818	81818188188	18111881818
88188188818	18818818888	18888181118	81111881118	81181118888	11811881118	81888188881	18181888881	18881881118	81118181118	81818188881	18111881118
11811818818	18818881811	81111818818	18888181811	81181181811	88188188188	18118188188	18181881811	81118188188	18881881811	81818181811	81888188188
11811888188	81181118118	18888118118	81111811818	18818888818	88188188818	18118888818	81818111811	18881811181	81118111181	18181888818	81888188818
11811811888	81181188811	81111888811	18888188811	18818811888	88188111888	18118111888	81818188811	81118188811	18881888811	18181111888	81888111888
88188188118	18818811888	81111888118	18888111888	81181118881	11811888118	81888188118	18181188881	81118188118	18881811888	81818118881	18111888118
88188181188	81181181188	18888188811	81111818881	18818881188	11811818881	81888181188	81818181188	18881818881	81118118881	18181881188	18111818881
88188188811	18818818881	18888181188	81111881188	81181118881	11811881188	81888188811	18181888811	18881881188	81118181188	81818188811	18111881188
11811818881	18818888118	81111818881	18888188118	81181188118	88188118881	18118118881	18181888118	81118118881	18881888118	81818188118	81888118881
11811888111	81181111888	18888111888	81111811888	18818888811	88188188811	18118888811	81818111888	18881811888	81118111888	18181888811	81888188811
1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982	1799999999982
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24

$1=(1,1)$	$11=(1,2)$	$21=(1,3)$	$31=(1,4)$	$41=(1,5)$	$51=(1,6)$	$61=(1,7)$
$2=(2,1)$	$12=(2,2)$	$22=(2,3)$	$32=(2,4)$	$42=(2,5)$	$52=(2,6)$	$62=(2,7)$
$3=(3,1)$	$13=(3,2)$	$23=(3,3)$	$33=(3,4)$	$43=(3,5)$	$53=(3,6)$	$63=(3,7)$
$4=(4,1)$	$14=(4,2)$	$24=(4,3)$	$34=(4,4)$	$44=(4,5)$	$54=(4,6)$	$64=(4,7)$
$5=(5,1)$	$15=(5,2)$	$25=(5,3)$	$35=(5,4)$	$45=(5,5)$	$55=(5,6)$	$65=(5,7)$
$6=(6,1)$	$16=(6,2)$	$26=(6,3)$	$36=(6,4)$	$46=(6,5)$	$56=(6,6)$	$66=(6,7)$
$7=(7,1)$	$17=(7,2)$	$27=(7,3)$	$37=(7,4)$	$47=(7,5)$	$57=(7,6)$	$67=(7,7)$

In this case, we get a **universal magic square** of order 42 with magic sum $S_{42 \times 42} := 209999999999979$. It is given below in three parts.

8111888888	1888188888	1881881111	8818811111	1811811111	8181818888	8118188888	1888188888	1818181111	8188111111	1118111111	8188888888	8188188888	1818188888
8111888881	1888111188	8181111188	1181888881	8188188881	1818181188	8118188881	1888181188	8181811188	1811888881	8888188881	1811111188	8188188881	1818111188
1888118888	8111818888	1881888111	1181818888	8188188111	8181888111	1888181888	8118118888	1818888111	1811818888	8888188111	8188888111	1818118888	8188181888
1888188111	8111888111	8181118888	1181888111	8188811888	1818181888	1888188111	8118188111	8181811888	1811888111	8888181888	1811118888	1818188111	8188188111
8111811188	1888188881	818188881	8818811188	1811811188	181888881	8118111188	1888188881	818188881	8188811188	1118111188	181188881	8188181188	1818188881
1888111111	8111811111	1881888888	8818818888	1811888888	8181811111	1888181111	8118111111	181888888	8188818888	1118188888	8188811111	1818111111	8188181111
8111888818	1888188818	1881881181	8818811181	1811811181	8181818818	8118188818	1888188818	1818181181	8188811181	1118111181	8188888818	8188188818	1818188818
8111888188	1888118111	8181118111	1181888188	8188818188	1818181811	8118188188	1888181811	8181811811	1811888188	8888188188	1811118111	8188188188	1818118111
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1888188188	8111888188	8181118811	1181888188	8188811881	1818181881	1888188818	8118188188	8181811881	1811888188	8888181881	1811118811	1818188188	8188188818
8111818111	1888188188	818188188	8818811811	1811818111	181888188	8118118111	1888188188	818188188	8188811811	1118118111	18118888	8188181111	181818888
1888111811	8111811811	1881888818	881881888	1811888818	8181811811	1888181181	8118111811	181888881	818881888	111818881	818881188	1818111888	8188181188
8111888181	1888188181	1881881818	881881818	181181818	8181818881	811818881	1888188881	181818118	818881818	111818118	818888881	818818881	181818881
8111881818	1888118181	8181118181	1181888181	8188818181	1818181818	8118188181	1888181818	818181818	1811888181	888818181	1811118181	8188188181	1818181818
1888188818	8111818881	1881888118	1181818881	8188818118	1818188818	1888188881	8118188818	1818881181	18118188818	8888188118	8188888118	1818188818	8188188881
1888181118	8111881118	818118881	1181881118	8188818881	1818188881	1888188118	8118181118	8181818881	1811881118	8888188881	1811188881	1818181118	8188188118
8111818888	1888188888	18818811181	88188111181	18118111181	8181818888	8118188888	1888188888	18181811181	81888111181	11181111181	8188888888	8188188888	1818188888
8111881888	1888118111	8181118111	11818881888	81888181888	18181818111	81181818888	18881818111	8181818111	18118881888	8888188888	1811181111	8188188888	1818181111
1888181818	8111818181	1881888188	1181818181	8188818888	1818188888	1888181818	8118181818	1818881888	1811818181	8888188888	8188888188	1818181818	8188181818
1888188818	8111888818	818118881	1181888818	8188818881	1818181881	1888188881	8118188818	8181818881	1811888818	8888188818	1811188818	1818188818	8188188881
8111818111	1888181888	81818888	8818818111	1811818111	1818881888	8118181111	1888188888	8181818888	8188818111	1118181111	1811818888	8188181111	181818888
1888111181	8111811181	18818888818	8818818888	18118888818	81818111181	18881811181	8118111181	181888881	8188818888	11181888818	8188811181	1818111181	81881811181
8111888811	1888188811	18818811888	88188111888	18118111888	81818188811	81181888811	18881888811	18181811888	81888111888	11181111888	8188888811	81881888811	1818188811
8111888118	1888118881	8181118881	1181888118	8188818818	18181818881	8118188118	18881818881	8181818881	1811888118	8888188118	1811118881	81881888118	1818118881
1888188811	8111818881	18818881188	1181818881	81888181188	18181888188	1888188881	8118188811	1818881188	1811818881	88881881188	81888881188	1818188811	8188188881
1888181188	8111881188	818118881	1181881188	8188818881	1818188881	18881881188	8118181188	8181818881	1811881188	8888188881	181118881	1818181188	81881881188
8111818881	1888188118	818188118	88188118881	18118188881	181888118	8118118881	18881888118	8181888118	81888118881	1118118881	181188118	81881818881	1818188118
1888111888	8111811888	1881888811	88188188811	1811888811	8181811888	18881811888	8118111888	181888811	81888188811	1118188811	8188811888	1818111888	81881811888
8111881818	1888181818	18818818881	88188181881	18118181881	818181818	8118181818	18881881818	1818181881	81888181881	1118181881	81888881818	81881881818	1818181818
8111881881	1888188118	8181188118	1181881881	81888181881	1818188818	8118181881	18881818818	8181818818	1811881881	88881881881	1811188118	81881881881	1818188118
1888188181	8111888181	18818881818	1181818881	81888181818	18181888181	1888188881	81181888181	1818881818	181181888181	88881881818	81888881818	18181888181	81881888181
1888181818	8111881818	8181188181	1181881818	81888188181	1818188818	18881881818	8118181818	81818188181	1811881818	88881888181	1811188181	1818181818	81881881818
8111818818	1888181881	8181818881	8818818818	1811818818	1818881881	811818818	188818881881	818188818	8188818818	111818818	1811818881	8188188818	1818181881
1888181881	811181881	18818881818	88188181881	18118881818	8181818881	18881818818	8118181881	1818881818	8188818818	1118181818	81888818881	1818181881	8188181881
209999999979	209999999979	209999999979	209999999979	209999999979	209999999979	209999999979	209999999979	209999999979	209999999979	209999999979	209999999979	209999999979	209999999979
15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28

$1=(1,1)$	$11=(1,2)$	$21=(1,3)$	$31=(1,4)$	$41=(1,5)$	$51=(1,6)$	$61=(1,7)$	$71=(1,8)$
$2=(2,1)$	$12=(2,2)$	$22=(2,3)$	$32=(2,4)$	$42=(2,5)$	$52=(2,6)$	$62=(2,7)$	$72=(2,8)$
$3=(3,1)$	$13=(3,2)$	$23=(3,3)$	$33=(3,4)$	$43=(3,5)$	$53=(3,6)$	$63=(3,7)$	$73=(3,8)$
$4=(4,1)$	$14=(4,2)$	$24=(4,3)$	$34=(4,4)$	$44=(4,5)$	$54=(4,6)$	$64=(4,7)$	$74=(4,8)$
$5=(5,1)$	$15=(5,2)$	$25=(5,3)$	$35=(5,4)$	$45=(5,5)$	$55=(5,6)$	$65=(5,7)$	$75=(5,8)$
$6=(6,1)$	$16=(6,2)$	$26=(6,3)$	$36=(6,4)$	$46=(6,5)$	$56=(6,6)$	$66=(6,7)$	$76=(6,8)$
$7=(7,1)$	$17=(7,2)$	$27=(7,3)$	$37=(7,4)$	$47=(7,5)$	$57=(7,6)$	$67=(7,7)$	$77=(7,8)$
$8=(8,1)$	$18=(8,2)$	$28=(8,3)$	$38=(8,4)$	$48=(8,5)$	$58=(8,6)$	$68=(8,7)$	$78=(8,8)$

In this case, we get a **universal magic square** of order 48 with magic sum $S_{48 \times 48} := 239999999999976$. It is given below in four parts:

$1=(1,1)$	$11=(1,2)$	$21=(1,3)$	$31=(1,4)$	$41=(1,5)$	$51=(1,6)$	$61=(1,7)$	$71=(1,8)$	$81=(1,9)$
$2=(2,1)$	$12=(2,2)$	$22=(2,3)$	$32=(2,4)$	$42=(2,5)$	$52=(2,6)$	$62=(2,7)$	$72=(2,8)$	$82=(2,9)$
$3=(3,1)$	$13=(3,2)$	$23=(3,3)$	$33=(3,4)$	$43=(3,5)$	$53=(3,6)$	$63=(3,7)$	$73=(3,8)$	$83=(3,9)$
$4=(4,1)$	$14=(4,2)$	$24=(4,3)$	$34=(4,4)$	$44=(4,5)$	$54=(4,6)$	$64=(4,7)$	$74=(4,8)$	$84=(4,9)$
$5=(5,1)$	$15=(5,2)$	$25=(5,3)$	$35=(5,4)$	$45=(5,5)$	$55=(5,6)$	$65=(5,7)$	$75=(5,8)$	$85=(5,9)$
$6=(6,1)$	$16=(6,2)$	$26=(6,3)$	$36=(6,4)$	$46=(6,5)$	$56=(6,6)$	$66=(6,7)$	$76=(6,8)$	$86=(6,9)$
$7=(7,1)$	$17=(7,2)$	$27=(7,3)$	$37=(7,4)$	$47=(7,5)$	$57=(7,6)$	$67=(7,7)$	$77=(7,8)$	$87=(7,9)$
$8=(8,1)$	$18=(8,2)$	$28=(8,3)$	$38=(8,4)$	$48=(8,5)$	$58=(8,6)$	$68=(8,7)$	$78=(8,8)$	$88=(8,9)$
$9=(9,1)$	$19=(9,2)$	$29=(9,3)$	$39=(9,4)$	$49=(9,5)$	$59=(9,6)$	$69=(9,7)$	$79=(9,8)$	$89=(9,9)$

In this case, we get a **universal magic square** of order 54 with magic sum $S_{54 \times 54} := 26999999999973$. It is given below in four parts:

3.9 Universal Magic Square of Order 60

Example 24. *Let's consider all the 100 magic squares of order 6 of type 10×10 given in Appendix 6 according to Table 1.2 or Figure 3.1, we have a **universal magic square** of order 60 with magic sum $S_{60 \times 60} := 299999999999970$. It is given below in four parts:*

4 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 12

In Appendix 7 there are total 25 magic squares of order 12. All of them are **universal pandiagonal magic squares** with **magic sums** $S_{12 \times 12}^n := 5999999999994$, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 25$. Let's write the Table 1.3 in the following way:

Figure 4.1.

The following subsections lead us to **universal pandiagonal magic squares** multiples of 12, i.e., of orders 12, 24, 36, 48 and 60. These are chosen according to colors appearing in the Figure 4.1. It is not the only way to write magic squares multiple of 12. The readers can chose alternative ways to write these magic squares.

4.1 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 12

Example 25. Let's consider a first magic square of order 12 given in Appendix 7:

12x12	pan	5999999999994	5999999999994	5999999999994	5999999999994	5999999999994	5999999999994	5999999999994	5999999999994	5999999999994	5999999999994	5999999999994	5999999999994
	118811818811	111111111111	118818181818	888888188881	881181118811	881188881181	188881811118	181188118818	181818881188	818181888888	811181818188	818811818181	5999999999994
5999999999994	118818111111	118811181818	111111818811	881181881181	881188188881	888888118811	181188881188	181818811118	188881118818	818811181188	818181818181	811188888888	5999999999994
5999999999994	111111818181	118818818811	118811111111	881188118811	888888881181	881181888881	181818188188	188881881188	181188811118	811188181818	818811888888	818181818188	5999999999994
5999999999994	881188881188	881181118818	888888811118	118818818181	111111818188	118811888888	818811181818	811181111111	818181818811	181818881181	181188118811	188881188881	5999999999994
5999999999994	888888118818	881188811118	881181881188	111111888888	118811818181	118818181188	811188188111	818181818188	818811111111	188881118811	181818188881	181188881181	5999999999994
5999999999994	881181811118	888888881188	881188118818	118811818188	118818888888	111111818181	818181111111	818811818811	811181818188	181188188881	188881881181	181818118811	5999999999994
5999999999994	811118188881	818811881181	818181118811	181818111111	188881818811	181188181818	881188181188	888888888888	881181818181	111111811118	118818881188	118811188188	5999999999994
5999999999994	818811118811	818181888881	811188811818	181188818811	181818181818	188881111111	881181888888	881188818181	888888181188	118818188188	118811811118	111118811888	5999999999994
5999999999994	818181881181	811181818811	818811888881	188881818188	181188111111	181818818811	888888818181	881181818188	881188888888	118811881188	111111881818	118818811118	5999999999994
5999999999994	181188818181	188881888888	181818181188	818181118818	818811881188	811188111118	118811188111	118818881181	111111888881	881181818188	888888188111	881188111111	5999999999994
5999999999994	188881181188	181818818181	181188888888	811188811888	818181811118	818811118818	111111881181	118811188881	118818188111	888888111111	881188181818	881181818811	5999999999994
5999999999994	181818888888	181188181188	188881818181	818811811118	811118188188	818181881188	118818188881	111111188111	118818811818	881188818811	881181111111	888888181818	5999999999994

In this case, we have a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 12 with magic sum $S_{12 \times 12} := 5999999999994$. This magic square is constructed with 16 blocks, where each block is a **semi-magic square** of order 3 with **different magic sums**. The same is true for all the 25 magic squares of order 12 given in Appendix 7.

4.2 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 24

Example 26. Let's consider 4 magic squares of order 12 of type 2×2 given in Appendix 7 according to Table 1.3 or as a part of Figure 4.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$5=(1,2)$
$2=(2,1)$	$6=(2,2)$

In this case, we get following **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 24 with magic sum $S_{24 \times 24} := 11999999999988$. It is given in below in two parts

24x24	pan	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	
		11881818811	11111111111	118818181818	888888188881	8818118811	8818888181	18888181118	1818818818	181888188	8181888888	8111818188	81881818181
11999999999988		11881811111	11881181818	11111818811	88181881181	88188188881	8888818811	1818888188	1818881118	18888118818	8188118188	8181818181	81118888888
11999999999988		11111181818	118818818811	11881111111	8818818811	88888888181	88181888881	18181818818	18888188188	1818881118	81118818181	81881888888	8181818188
11999999999988		8818888188	8818118818	88888811118	118818818181	1111118188	11881888888	81881181818	8111811111	81818188811	181888181	1818818811	18888188881
11999999999988		88888818818	8818881118	8818188188	11111888888	11881818181	11881818188	81118818811	81818181818	81881111111	18888118811	18181888881	1818888181
11999999999988		8818181118	8888888188	8818818818	1188118188	11881888888	11111818181	81818111111	81881818811	81118181818	18188188881	18888188181	18181818811
11999999999988		81118188881	8188188181	81818118811	18181811111	188881818811	18188181818	8818818188	88888888888	88181818181	1111181118	11881888188	11881118818
11999999999988		81881118811	81818188881	8111888181	18188818811	181818181818	18888111111	88181888888	88188818181	8888818188	11881818818	1188181118	1111188188
11999999999988		81818188181	81118188811	81881188881	18888181818	18188111111	18188818811	88888818181	881818188	88188888888	1188188188	1111118818	11881881118
11999999999988		18188818181	188881888888	18181818188	81818118818	8188188188	8111881118	11881118811	11881888181	11111188881	8818181818	88888818811	8818811111
11999999999988		1888818188	18188818181	18188888888	8111888188	81818181118	81881118818	1111188181	11881188881	11881818811	8888811111	88188181818	88181818811
11999999999988		181818888888	1818818188	188881818181	8188181118	8111818818	81818188188	11881818881	1111118811	1188188181	88188818811	8818111111	888888181818
11999999999988		11881881888	1111111181	11881818888	88888818111	8818111188	88188888188	18888181888	1818811811	18181888881	818181888818	81118181811	81881881111
11999999999988		11881811181	11881118888	11111881888	88181888188	88188181111	8888811188	18188888811	18181881888	18888111811	81881118111	81818188111	81118888818
11999999999988		11111118888	118818881888	1188111181	8818811188	888888888188	88181818111	18181811811	18888188881	18188818888	81118881111	81881888818	81818118111
11999999999988		8818888881	8818111811	88888818888	11881888111	1111118111	11881888818	81881118888	8111811181	818181881888	181818888188	1818811188	18888181111
11999999999988		88888811811	88188818888	88181888811	11111888818	11881881111	11881818111	81118881888	81818118888	8188111181	18888111188	18181818111	18188888188
11999999999988		88181818888	888888888811	8818811811	11881118111	11881888818	11111881111	8181811181	81881881888	81118188888	18188181111	188881888188	18181811188
11999999999988		81118181111	81881888188	8181811188	18181811181	188881881888	1818818888	8818818111	88888888818	88181881111	11111818888	118818888811	1188111811
11999999999988		81881111188	81818181111	81118888188	18188881888	18181818888	18888111181	88181888818	88188881111	88888818111	11881811811	11881818888	11111888811
11999999999988		818181888188	8111811188	81881181111	18888118888	1818811181	18188881888	88888881111	88181818111	88188888818	11881888811	1111111811	118818818888
11999999999988		18188881111	188881888818	18181818111	81818111811	81881888811	81118818888	1188111188	118818888188	11111181111	8818118888	88888881888	8818811181
11999999999988		18888118111	181818881111	18188888818	81118888811	818181818888	81881111811	11111888188	11881181111	11881811188	88888811181	88188188888	88181881888
11999999999988		181818888818	18188181111	188881881111	81881818888	8111811811	818181888811	11881818111	1111111188	11881888188	88188881888	8818111181	88888818888
		11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988	11999999999988
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988
1118881881	1118111111	1181181818	8888181888	8881881881	8888188181	1811181118	1811118818	1888881188	8811188888	8188881818	8818881818	119999999988	
1181111111	11188181818	1118181881	88818888181	8888118888	8888181881	1811188188	1888881118	1811118818	88188818188	8811181818	81888888888	119999999988	
1118181818	118181881	1118811111	8888111881	88881888181	8881881888	1888818818	1811188188	1811181118	81888818181	88188888888	8811181818	119999999988	
8888188188	88818818818	8888881118	1181818181	11181818188	11188888888	881888181818	81888811111	8811181881	188888181	1181118881	18111188881	119999999988	
88881818818	8888181118	88818888188	11181888888	11188818181	1118118188	81888881881	88111181818	88188811111	181111881	18888188881	1181188181	119999999988	
88818881118	888888188	88881118818	1118818188	118188888	11181818181	8811111111	8818888181	8188881818	11811188881	1811188181	188881881	119999999988	
818888188881	88188888181	8811111881	1888811111	1811181881	11811181818	8888118188	88881888888	888188818181	1118181118	118188188	1118818818	119999999988	
8818881881	88111188881	81888888181	1811181881	18888181818	1811111111	88818888888	88881818181	88881818188	1181118818	1118881118	1118188188	119999999988	
8811188181	8188881881	881888188881	18111181818	1181111111	1888881881	88881881818	88818818188	88881888888	1118888188	1118118818	1118181118	119999999988	
11811818181	18111888888	1888818188	88111118818	88188888188	81888881118	111881881	1118188181	1118188881	888188181818	8888188181	8888111111	119999999988	
1811118188	18888818181	11811888888	8188888188	8811181118	88188818818	1118188181	11188188881	118111881	8888181111	88881181818	88818881881	119999999988	
18888888888	18111818188	18111818181	88188881118	81888818818	8811188188	11181188881	111811881	1118888181	8888181881	8881881111	8888181818	119999999988	
11188881888	1118111181	11181118888	88881818111	88818811188	88881888188	18111818888	181111181	1888888881	88111888818	8188881811	8818888111	119999999988	
11181111181	1118818888	11181881888	888188888188	8888118111	88881811188	1181188881	18888818888	181111181	8818881811	8811188111	81888888818	119999999988	
1118118888	1181881888	1118811181	8888111188	88881888188	88818818111	188881181	1811188881	11811818888	81888888111	88188888818	881111811	119999999988	
8888188881	8881881181	88881881888	118188111	111811811	11188888818	88188818888	81888811181	88111881888	18888888188	1181111188	181118111	119999999988	
8888181181	88881818888	88818888881	11181888818	1118888111	1118111811	818888881888	8811118888	88188811181	1811111188	1888818111	11811888188	119999999988	
888188818888	88881888881	888811181	111881811	11181888818	1118188111	8811111181	881888881888	81888818888	1181118111	18111888188	1888811188	119999999988	
81888818111	881888888188	8811111188	1888811181	18111881888	1181118888	8888111811	888818888818	88818888111	11181818888	118188881	1118818181	119999999988	
88188811188	8811118111	818888888188	11811881888	1888818888	1811111181	88818888818	8888188111	8888181811	118111181	11188818888	1118188881	119999999988	
88111888188	81888811188	88188818111	1811118888	1181111181	18888881888	88881888111	8881881811	88881888818	111888881	111811181	11181818888	119999999988	
1181188111	18111888818	188881811	881111181	8818888881	818888818888	1118811188	11181888188	111818111	88818818888	888818881888	8888111181	119999999988	
181111811	1888888111	11811888818	8188888881	88111818888	8818881181	11181888188	1118818111	1118111188	88881811181	88881118888	888188881888	119999999988	
18888888818	118111811	1811188111	881888818888	8188881181	8811188881	1118118111	1118111188	11188888188	88881881888	88818811181	88881818888	119999999988	
119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	119999999988	
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24		

4.3 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 36

Example 27. Let's consider 9 magic squares of order 12 of type 3×3 given in Appendix 7 according to Table 1.3 or as a part of Figure 4.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$11=(1,2)$	$21=(1,3)$
$2=(2,1)$	$12=(2,2)$	$22=(2,3)$
$3=(3,1)$	$13=(3,2)$	$23=(3,3)$

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 36 with magic sum $S_{36 \times 36} := 1799999999982$. It is given below in three parts.

4.5 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 60

Example 29. *Let's consider all the 25 magic squares of order 12 of type 5×5 given in Appendix 7 according to Table 1.3 or as a part of Figure 4.1, we have a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 12 with magic sum $S_{60 \times 60} := 29999999999970$. It is given below in five parts:*

99.

11881811818	818811888181	818188888181	181811888181	181188111818	88118111818
881181881818	181188118181	818188881818	18181118181	81881118181	118818881818
88118181811	81881181811	181811181888	818188181888	18118881811	118818181888
88118181888	181188181888	18181181811	81818881811	818811181888	11881881811
118818118181	181188881818	818188118181	181811881818	818811881818	881181118181
118818888181	81881111818	18181111818	81818811818	181188888181	881181888181

100.

118818118818	818811881181	818188881181	181811881181	181188118818	881181118818
881181818811	181188181188	818188818811	181811181188	818811181188	118818818811
881181818188	818811818188	181811181811	818188181811	181188818188	118818181811
881181181811	181188181811	181811818188	818188818188	818811181811	118818818188
118818181188	181188818811	818188181188	18181188811	81881188811	881181181188
118818881181	818811118818	181811118818	818188118818	181188881181	881181881181

7 Appendix: Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 12

1.

118811818811	111111111111	118818181818	888888188881	881181188811	881188881181	188881811118	181188118818	181818881188	818181888888	81118181188	818811818181
118818111111	11881181818	111111818811	881181881181	881188188881	888888118811	181188881188	181818811118	188881118818	818811181188	818181818181	81118888888
11111181818	118818818811	118811111111	881188118811	888888881181	881181188881	181818118818	188881881188	181188811118	81118818181	818811888888	818181818188
881188881188	88118118818	888888811118	118818818181	111111818188	118811888888	818811181818	811181111111	818181818811	181818881181	181188118811	188881188881
888888118818	881188811118	881181881188	111111888888	118811818181	118818181188	81118818811	818181181818	818811111111	188881118811	181818188881	181188881181
881181811118	888888881188	881188118818	118811818188	118818888888	111111818181	818181111111	818811818811	81118181818	181188188881	188881881181	18181818811
811181888881	818811881181	818181188811	181818111111	188881818811	181188181818	881188181188	888888888888	881181818181	11111811118	118818881188	11881118818
81881118811	818181888881	81118881181	181188818811	181818181818	188881111111	881181888888	881188818181	888888181188	11881818818	118811811118	11111881188
81818881181	81118188811	818811188881	18888181818	181188111111	181818818811	888888818181	881181818188	881188888888	118811881188	11111118818	118818811118
181188818181	188881888888	181818181188	81818118818	818811881188	81118811118	11881118811	118818881181	111111888881	88118181818	888888818811	881188111111
18888181188	181818818181	181188888888	81118881188	818181811118	81881118818	11111881181	118811188881	11881818811	888888111111	881188181818	881181818811
181818888888	181188181188	188881818181	818811811118	811181818818	818181881188	118818188881	11111118811	118811881181	881188818811	881181111111	888888181818

2.

111188818811	111181111111	111811181818	888818188881	888188118811	888811881181	18111811118	11811118818	11888881188	881111888888	818888181188	881888818181
111811111111	111188181818	111181818811	888188881181	88881188881	888818118811	11811881188	118888811118	18111118818	881888181188	88111818181	818888888888
11118181818	111811818811	111188111111	88881118811	888818881181	888188188881	118888118818	18111881188	11811811118	818888818181	881888888888	881111818188
888811881188	888188118818	888818811118	111811818181	111181818188	111188888888	881888181818	818888111111	88111818811	11888881181	11811118811	181111888881
888818118818	888811811118	888188881188	111181888888	111188818181	111811818188	818888818811	88111181818	881888111111	18111118811	118888188881	11811881181
888188811118	888818881188	88881118818	11118818188	111811888888	111181818181	881111111111	881888818811	818888181818	118111888881	18111881181	118888118811
818888188881	881888881181	88111118811	118888111111	18111818811	11811181818	888811818188	888818888888	888188818181	11181811118	11811881188	11118818818
881888118811	881111188881	818888881181	11811818811	118888181818	181111111111	888188888888	88881818181	88881818188	11811118818	111188811118	111181881188
881111881181	818888118811	881888188881	18111181818	118111111111	118888818811	888818818181	888188181188	888811888888	111188881188	11181118818	118181811118
118111818181	181111888888	118888181188	88111118818	881888881188	818888811118	111188118811	11811881181	111181888881	888188181818	888818818811	888811111111
181111818188	118888818181	118118888888	818888881188	88111811118	881888118818	11118811881	111188188881	1181118811	888818111111	88881181818	888188818811
118888888888	11811181188	18111818181	881888811118	818888118818	88111881188	118111888881	11118118811	111188881181	88881818811	888811111111	888818181818

3.

1181818811	11818111111	18118181818	881881188881	81888118811	881818881181	188818811118	18181118818	188188881188	811811888888	81181181188	818188818181
181181111111	11818181818	11818818811	818881881181	881818188881	88188118811	18181881188	188188811118	188818118818	818188181188	811811818181	811181888888
118118181818	18118818811	118181111111	88181818811	881881881181	818881188881	188188118818	188818881188	18181811118	81181818181	818188888888	818181181188
881818881188	81888118818	881881811118	18118818181	118118181188	118181888888	818188181818	811811111111	811811818811	188188881181	18181118811	188818188881
88188118818	881818811118	818881881188	118188888888	118181818181	181181818188	811181818811	811811181818	818188111111	188818118811	188188188881	18181881181
818881811118	881881881188	88181818818	118181818188	181188888888	11818818181	811811111111	818188818811	81118181818	181811188881	188818881181	188188118811
811181888881	818188881181	81181118811	188188111111	188818818811	18181181818	88181818188	881881888888	818881818181	11818811118	18118881188	11818118818
818188118811	811811188881	81118188181	18181818811	188188181818	188818111111	818881888888	881881818181	881881181188	1811818818	1181811118	11818881188
811811881181	81118118811	818188188881	188818181818	181811111111	188188818811	881881818181	818881181188	881818888888	11818881188	1181818818	18118811118
181811818181	188818888888	188188181188	81181118818	818188881188	811181811118	11818118811	1811888181	118118188881	81888181818	881881818811	881818111111
188818181188	188188818181	181818888888	811181881188	811811811118	81818818818	1181888181	118181188881	1811818811	881881111111	8818181818	818881818811
188188888888	18181181188	188818818181	818188811118	81118118818	811811881188	181181888881	118118118811	11818881181	88188818811	818881111111	88188181818

24.

118881818818	111888111818	181881181888	888111188111	818118111881	881118881811	188811811888	188118118188	188181888118	811818888181	811888181181	811881818111
181881111818	118881181888	111888818818	818118881811	881118188111	888111111881	18818888118	18818181888	18881118188	81188181181	811818818111	81188888181
111888181888	181881818818	11888111818	881118111881	888111881811	818118188111	18818118188	188811888118	1881881888	81188818111	811881888181	811818181181
881118888118	818118118188	888111811888	181881818111	111888181181	118881888181	811881181888	81188111818	811818818818	188181881811	18818111881	188811188111
88811118188	881118811888	818118888118	111888888181	118881818111	181881181181	81188818818	811818181888	81188111818	18881111881	188181188111	18818881811
818118811888	888111888118	881118118188	118881181181	181881888181	111888818111	811818111818	811881818818	81188181888	18818188111	188811881811	18818111881
81188188111	811881881811	811818111881	188181111818	188811818818	188118181888	88811111818	818118888181	881118818111	888111818181	181881118188	118881811888
811818881811	81118811881	811881188111	188811181888	18818111818	18818181888	888111818111	81811818181	881118888181	118881888118	11888118188	18188181888
18818818111	188811888181	188181181181	811818181888	811881888118	81188811888	11888111881	181881881811	11888188111	818118181888	888111818818	881118111818
188811181181	188181818111	18818888181	81188888118	811818811888	811881118188	11888881811	118881188111	18188111881	88811111818	88118181888	81818818818
188181888181	188118181181	188811818111	81188181888	81188118188	811818888118	181881188111	1188811881	118881881811	88111818818	818118111818	88811181888

25.

111881818818	111818111818	118188181888	888181188111	881811111881	88818881811	188111811888	181181118188	18188888118	818111888181	811888181181	818818818111
118188111818	111881181888	111818818818	881811881811	888118188111	888181111881	181181888118	181888811888	18811118188	81881818181	818111818111	81188888181
111818181888	118188818818	11188111818	888181111881	888181881811	881811188111	181888118188	188111888118	18118181888	811888818111	818818888181	818111181181
888118888118	881811118188	888181811888	118188818111	111818181181	111881888181	818818181888	811888111818	818111818818	181888881811	18118111881	188111188111
888181118188	888118811888	881811888118	111818888181	111881818111	118188181181	811888818818	818111181888	818818111818	18811111881	181888188111	181181881811
881811818888	888181888118	888181181888	111881181181	118188888181	111818818111	818111111818	818818818818	811888181888	181181188111	188111881811	181888111881
811888188111	818818881811	818111111881	181888111818	188111818818	181181181888	888118181181	888181888181	881811818111	111818811888	118188888118	111881118188
818818111881	818111188111	811888881811	181181818818	181888181888	188111111818	881811888181	88818818111	888181181181	118188118188	11188181888	111818888118
818111881811	811888111881	818818188111	188111181888	181181111818	181888818818	888181818111	881811181181	888118888181	111881888118	11181818188	118188811888
181181818111	188111888181	181888181181	81811118188	818818888118	811888811888	11188111881	118188881811	111818188111	881811181888	888181818818	88818111818
188111181181	181888818111	181181888181	811888888118	81811181888	818818118188	111818881811	111881188111	118188111881	888181111818	88818181888	881811818818
181888888181	181181181181	188111818111	818818811888	811888118188	818111888118	118188188111	111818111881	111881881811	88818818818	881811111818	888181181888

8 Author's Contributions to Magic Squares

The **item-wise** author's work on magic squares is as follows:

1. **Digital Numbers Magic Squares** - [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 37];
2. **Block-Wise Construction of Bimagic Squares** - [11];
3. **Connections with Genetic Tables and Shannon's entropy** - [12];
4. **Selfie and Palindromic-type Magic Squares** - [13, 28, 37];
5. **Intervally Distributed and Block-Wise Magic Squares** - [14, 15, 16, 28];
6. **Multi-digits and Number Patterns Magic Squares** - [17, 27];
7. **Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares with Uniformity, Minimum Sum and Pythagorean Triples** - [18, 19];
8. **Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares** - [20, 21, 22, 23, 26, 29, 31];
9. **Magic Crosses: Repeated and Non Repeated Entries** - [24];
10. **Representations of Letters and Numbers With Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders 4 and 6** - [25].
11. **Bordered Magic Squares** - [32, 33, 34, 35, 36].
12. **2-Digits Magic and Bimagic Squares** - [38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43].

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